

A Comparative Analysis of Deep Learning for Vehicle Make-Model-Year Image Classification

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Abstract

This project focuses on developing an image classification model to accurately identify the Make, Model, and Year of vehicles using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The process involved extensive data preprocessing, model training, and hyperparameter tuning, utilising both PyTorch and TensorFlow frameworks. Despite the steep learning curve and complexities in understanding CNNs and deep learning models, the project successfully leveraged transfer learning techniques with pre-trained models like ResNet50, VGG16, VGG19, etc. A custom web application was developed using Next.js, integrating the final ResNet50 model to provide real-time vehicle classification and pricing information. The application also incorporates fallback mechanisms using OpenAI's GPT-4o vision capabilities and eBay's API for comprehensive user interactions. This project highlights the challenges and rewards of combining advanced machine learning techniques with practical web development to create a functional and user-friendly tool.

Video Demo of Website: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZUQtKNNMFQ>

Table of Contents

Abstract.....	ii
Table of Contents.....	iii
List of Tables.....	vi
List of Figures.....	vii
List of Appendices.....	x
1. Introduction.....	1
2. Aims & Objectives.....	3
2.1. Primary Aim.....	3
2.2. Objectives.....	3
3. Methodology.....	5
3.1. Research Problem Classification.....	5
3.2. Types of Data Collected.....	5
3.3. Tools and Dependencies for Completion.....	6
3.4. Process.....	7
3.5. Classification of the Conclusion.....	8
4. Models & CNNs Context Literature.....	10
4.1. Convolutional Neural Networks.....	10
4.1.1. Convolution Layer.....	12
4.1.2. ReLU Layer.....	13
4.1.3. Pooling Layer.....	14
4.1.4. Fully Connected Layer.....	15
4.2. Pre-Trained Models.....	16
4.2.1. ResNet50 Model.....	16
4.2.2. VGG16 Model.....	18
4.2.3. VGG19 Model.....	19
5. Data Collection & Preprocessing.....	20

5.1.	Data Collection	20
5.1.1.	Defined Classes.....	21
5.1.2.	Scraping Process	21
5.1.3.	Semi-Final Resulting Dataset	22
5.2.	Preprocessing	23
5.2.1.	File Structure.....	23
5.2.2.	Preprocessing.ipynb Script	24
5.2.3.	Final Preprocessed Dataset	27
6.	Model Implementation	28
6.1.	Optimisers & Loss Functions.....	28
6.1.1.	Categorical Cross Entropy	28
6.1.2.	Adam.....	29
6.1.3.	RMSprop.....	30
6.2.	Tensorflow Implementation (FINAL MODEL)	31
6.3.	PyTorch *Alternate* Implementation.....	46
7.	Results & Discussion	53
7.1.	Final Model Results	54
8.	Website Implementation	56
8.1.	Directory Structure.....	56
8.2.	Explanation & Implementation.....	58
8.2.1.	TensorFlow .h5 Conversion.....	58
8.2.2.	Loading Model Client-Side in Browser.....	60
8.2.3.	Making Predictions	61
8.2.4.	OpenAI Fallback API	64
8.2.5.	eBay API.....	70
8.2.6.	Middleware Rate Limiting.....	74
8.2.7.	Vercel – CI/CD + GitHub	76

8.3. Designs, Showcase & Video Demo	78
9. Conclusion	89
9.1. Further Research	89
10. References	90
11. Appendices	94

List of Tables

Table 1 - Manual Images Review Before Preprocessing.....	22
Table 2 - Final Preprocessed Resulting Dataset	27
Table 3 - Final Model Results.....	54

List of Figures

Figure 1 - How CNN Classifies Image (Huellmann, 2022).....	11
Figure 2 - Convolution Operation on a 7x7 matrix with a 3x3 kernel (Basavarajaiah, 2019).12	12
Figure 3 - ReLU Operation (Raghav, 2018)	13
Figure 4 - Max Pooling Application (Raghav, 2018)	14
Figure 5 - CNN with Fully Connected Layer (developersbreach, 2024).....	15
Figure 6 - ResNet50 Architecture (Kundu, 2023)	16
Figure 7 - Residual Block (Choudhary, 2023).....	17
Figure 8 - VGG16 Architecture (Rohini G, 2021).....	18
Figure 9 - VGG16 vs VGG19 (Ahmad, 2023)	19
Figure 10 - Preprocessing File Structure	23
Figure 11 - Preprocessing Script Part 1.....	24
Figure 12 - Preprocessing Script Part 2.....	25
Figure 13 - Preprocessing Script Part 3.....	26
Figure 14 - How Adam Works (Vishwakarma, 2024).....	29
Figure 15 - Tensorflow Step 1	31
Figure 16 - Tensorflow Step 2	32
Figure 17 - Tensorflow Step 3	32
Figure 18 - Tensorflow Step 4	33
Figure 19 - Tensorflow Step 5	34
Figure 20 - Tensorflow Step 6	35
Figure 21 - Tensorflow Step 7	35
Figure 22 - Tensorflow Step 8	36
Figure 23 - Tensorflow Step 9	37
Figure 24 - Tensorflow Step 10	38
Figure 25 - Tensorflow Step 11	39
Figure 26 - Tensorflow Step 12	39
Figure 27 - Tensorflow Step 13	40
Figure 28 - Tensorflow Step 14	41
Figure 29 - Tensorflow Step 15	41
Figure 30 - Tensorflow Step 16	42
Figure 31 - Tensorflow Step 17	42
Figure 32 - Tensorflow Step 18	43

Figure 33 - Tensorflow Step 19	43
Figure 34 - Tensorflow Step 20	44
Figure 35 - Tensorflow Step 21	44
Figure 36 - PyTorch Step 1	46
Figure 37 - PyTorch Step 2	47
Figure 38 - PyTorch Step 3	47
Figure 39 - PyTorch Step 4	48
Figure 40 - PyTorch Step 5	48
Figure 41 - PyTorch Step 6	49
Figure 42 - PyTorch Step 7	50
Figure 43 - PyTorch Step 8	51
Figure 44 - PyTorch Step 9	51
Figure 45 - PyTorch Step 10	52
Figure 46 - PyTorch Step 11	52
Figure 47 - Tensorflowjs_converter command	59
Figure 48 - Tensorflowjs_converter Output	59
Figure 49 - Downloading & Caching Model	60
Figure 50 - Tfjs Prediction	62
Figure 51 - Prediction Flowchart	63
Figure 52 - /api/predictImage Part 1	64
Figure 53 - /api/predictImage Part 2	65
Figure 54 - /api/predictImage Part 3	66
Figure 55 - callPredictAPI Client-Side Part 1	67
Figure 56 - callPredictAPI Client-Side Part 2	68
Figure 57 - callPredictAPI Client-Side Part 3	69
Figure 58 - /api/getEbay Part 1	71
Figure 59 - /api/getEbay Part 2	72
Figure 60 - /api/getEbay Part 3	73
Figure 61 - Middleware Part 1	74
Figure 62 - Middleware Part 2	75
Figure 63 - Vercel CI/CD Pipeline	76
Figure 64 - Part of the GitHub README.md	77
Figure 65 - NeuroCar Loading [Desktop]	78
Figure 66 - NeuroCar Loading [Mobile]	78

Figure 67 - NeuroCar Home [Desktop]	79
Figure 68 - NeuroCar Home [Mobile]	79
Figure 69 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P1 [Desktop]	80
Figure 70 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P1 [Mobile]	81
Figure 71 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 [Desktop]	82
Figure 72 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 [Mobile]	82
Figure 73 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 ResNet50 [Desktop]	83
Figure 74 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 ResNet50 [Mobile]	84
Figure 75 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P3 [Desktop]	85
Figure 76 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P3 [Mobile]	85
Figure 77 - NeuroCar FinalPage [Desktop]	86
Figure 78 - NeuroCar FinalPage [Mobile]	87

List of Appendices

Appendix 1 – VGG19 Model Performance

Appendix 2 – VGG16 Model Performance

1. Introduction

This assignment involved developing an image classification model to identify the make, model, and year of vehicles from images. The project, mostly, aimed to apply deep learning techniques, mainly that from Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to improve decision-making through image recognition. As per (Huang, 2023), *“CNNs are specifically designed to process data that has a grid-like structure, such as images, and are capable of automatically learning and extracting features from this data. This allows CNNs to perform tasks such as image classification and object detection with high accuracy”*. Vehicle make-model-year classification is particularly challenging due to the fine and granular details of different cars. Unlike the more general object classification, like hands or fruit or shapes, etc, this task requires the model to distinguish between subtle differences in vehicle designs, which can be troublesome due to the similarity among many cars. Factors such as lighting, angles, logos, interiors, exteriors, are just a few of the things to watch out for in the dataset, and using a CNN was an obvious choice.

The project utilised quite a diverse dataset of vehicle images, encompassing multiple categories corresponding to different makes, models, and years. This dataset was painstakingly and manually collected which took a considerable amount of time. The datasets out there weren't in a good format to use for the project.

Extensive data preprocessing was performed, including resizing images, normalising pixel values, etc, and splitting the dataset into training and validation sets. Two models were developed using PyTorch *and* Tensorflow, both machine learning frameworks that *“simplifies machine learning algorithms [and] lets you develop ML models easily, without understanding the underlying algorithms [in its most granular form]”* as stated by (Johnson & Rowe, 2020), all to allow for a deeper understanding of both frameworks when modifying layers in a pre-trained model, also known as Transfer Learning. *“Transfer learning (TL) is a machine learning (ML) technique where a model pre-trained on one task is fine-tuned for a new, related task”* (AWS, 2024). Among this, several challenges were anticipated, including the granularity of the classification task, which required fine-tuning the model to accurately identify similar vehicle features. Hyperparameter tuning was essential to optimise the model's

accuracy and reduce loss metrics, involving careful analysis and correction of misclassifications and errors, all using accuracy as a primary metric.

After using PyTorch and Tensorflow, as well as testing with different pre-trained models, etc, one final model was decided upon with the adjusted hyperparameters and preprocessing flow, and utilised strategically in a custom-made web application, available for anyone to use for free at <https://neurocar.net>. (To run and setup locally as well as view the source code, visit <https://github.com/HaynesX/ai2>). The web application uses the final model to predict Make, Model, Year of a select few cars. If the model cannot predict a car, it uses OpenAI's 'gpt-4o' LLM+Vision model via an API to find the Make, Model and Year instead, as a fallback. *"GPT-4o is 2x faster, half the price, and has 5x higher rate limits compared to GPT-4 Turbo"* (OpenAI, 2024). After the vehicle details have been found, the website will utilise the eBay API to aggregate live listings to give the user the average price of the car classified as well as providing the user with said listings to view and see for themselves, all through the "Finding API", which is essentially a *"A searching API that allows you to search and browse for items listed on eBay, [as well as] provide useful metadata"* (eBay, 2024). It was imperative that the model served some sense of purpose for a proof-of-concept. People don't usually make models and not use them for something meaningful, so it seemed fitting for the assignment.

From model testing and learning, to a live production-grade serverless web application, the assignment given was certainly a challenging task to complete, and provides more context specifically in addressing a niche gap for identifying Make, Model, Year of cars effectively through a modified pre-trained model, identifying challenges and many more key aspects of Image Classification as a whole.

2. Aims & Objectives

The Aims and Objectives section outlines the primary goals and specific steps necessary to achieve the project's desired outcomes. This section provides some clarity on what the assignment intends to accomplish overall. Defining super clear aims and objectives allows for a structured approach to the project, allowing for effective planning, execution, and evaluation.

2.1. Primary Aim

Develop an image classification model to accurately identify the make, model, and year of vehicles using a wide range of deep learning techniques, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), with an end goal of using a tuned model via Transfer Learning on a website to predict the average price of a given vehicle.

2.2. Objectives

Dataset Selection: Research as well as select a diverse dataset of vehicle images, ensuring it includes multiple categories (classes) for different makes, models, and years.

Data Preprocessing: Perform data preprocessing steps such as resizing images, normalising pixel values, and augmenting data to enhance the model's training process, as well as manually go over images by hand to ensure a more accurate prediction.

Model Development: Utilise *PyTorch* and *TensorFlow* frameworks to develop and train a few models, leveraging transfer learning with pre-trained models for improved performance.

Hyperparameter Tuning: Do some hyperparameter tuning to optimise the model's accuracy and minimise loss, adjusting parameters based on validation results.

Model Evaluation: Test the final model using a separate testing dataset and evaluate its performance using accuracy.

Web Application Integration: Deploy the final model in a web application, allowing users to predict vehicle make, model, and year and access related eBay listings for price comparison.

Fallback Mechanism: Implement a fallback mechanism using OpenAI's GPT-4 model via an API to ensure predictions are available even when the primary model fails.

Documentation: Document the entire process, including dataset selection, data preprocessing, model development, evaluation, and integration into the web application, ensuring clarity and reproducibility.

3. Methodology

The Methodology section outlines the guided approach taken to achieve the assignment's objectives and overall aim, detailing the processes, tools, and techniques used. This section is quite important for understanding *how* the results were achieved and provides a framework for replicating the results. The methodology was planned to ensure the project's success. It's important to note here that the Methodology below acts as a *guide* to how the assignment was conducted, and does not go through the **actual** processes and results – that is shown in the sections thereafter!

3.1. Research Problem Classification

The classified research problem would be, essentially, defined as a **multi-class image classification task**. This involved developing a model capable of distinguishing between various makes, models, and years of vehicles based on images. The complexity of this problem required a deep learning approach, leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to extract and learn from the fine-grained features present in the vehicle images.

Although a website was made to show a proof-of-concept, it was not the sole focus of the Assignment.

3.2. Types of Data Collected

The data collected for this project consisted of a diverse set of vehicle images representing different makes, models, and years. The dataset included images from various sources, ensuring a wide range of conditions such as different lighting, angles, and backgrounds. This was crucial for training a good model capable of generalising well to new, unseen images. They are secondary sources of images rather than taken first-hand in real life, and are all manually checked and automatically preprocessed.

3.3. Tools and Dependencies for Completion

A variety of tools and dependencies were employed to complete the assignment.

Frameworks and Libraries: PyTorch and TensorFlow (including Keras) were used for model development and training. *“Keras is the high-level API of the TensorFlow platform. It provides an approachable, highly-productive interface for solving machine learning (ML) problems, with a focus on modern deep learning. Keras covers every step of the machine learning workflow, from data processing to hyperparameter tuning to deployment.”*

(TensorFlow, 2024). These frameworks facilitated the implementation of CNN architectures and transfer learning.

Programming Languages: Python3 was the primary language used for coding the machine learning models. JavaScript, TypeScript, and Node.js were used for developing the web application.

Development Environments: Google Colab provided the computational resources needed for training the models, including GPU access, which was supplemented by purchasing 100 credits out of the researcher of the assignment’s own money! (There was an implicit dedication for the assignment 😊). Visual Studio Code (VS Code) was used for coding the website.

Web Technologies: Next.js and Vercel were used for web application deployment. Additional tools included Vercel KV for rate limiting, TensorFlow.js (tfjs) for running models in the browser, and NextUI for user interface design.

APIs: OpenAI API was integrated for fallback predictions, and the eBay API was used to provide real-time vehicle listings and pricing information.

Other Tools: GitHub was used for version control and continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD), and various open-source packages such as Framer Motion for animations on the website were incorporated.

3.4. Process

The process involved several key steps to ensure a comprehensive and effective approach to solving the image classification problem as well as for the website to made nicely.

Dataset Preparation:

The dataset was manually collected, ensuring a diverse set of vehicle images encompassing various makes, models, and years. This included images from multiple sources such as Google Images, Shutterstock and eBay. Images were resized to a consistent dimension and normalised to ensure uniform pixel value ranges. This preprocessing was important to prepare the data for training. The dataset was split into training and validation sets for model evaluation as well as deal with overfitting properly.

Model Development:

Many models were tested using PyTorch and TensorFlow frameworks. Transfer learning was applied by modifying layers of pre-trained models, such as ResNet50 and VGG16. This approach leveraged existing knowledge from large-scale datasets to enhance performance on the specific task of vehicle classification. Various model architectures and configurations of hyperparams were experimented with to identify the most effective setup for the classification.

Training and Tuning:

Models were trained on Google Colab using GPUs to make the training process go a LOT faster. The computational power provided by Colab was absolutely essential. Hyperparameter tuning was performed to optimise model performance and took up a large amount of time of the project trying to get high accuracy by adjusting many parameters. This involved adjusting parameters such as learning rate, batch size, the number of epochs, augmentation layers, etc, all to achieve the best accuracy and minimise loss metrics. Multiple models and configurations were tested to find the *most* accurate and reliable model for the classification task, with a strong avoidance of overfitting.

Evaluation:

The metrics provided a good assessment of the models' effectiveness in classifying vehicle images, such as accuracy and loss. The evaluation process mainly involved testing the models on the validation and training sets to ensure their ability to generalise cars properly across classes. Lastly, **one final model was chosen** based on its high accuracy and balanced performance across all evaluation metrics.

Web Application Development:

The final model was integrated into a web application developed using Next.js and deployed on Vercel. This provided a user-friendly interface for accessing the model's predictions. TensorFlow.js was used to run the model directly in the browser, enhancing the application's responsiveness and accessibility. There was an initial attempt to deploy to Vertex AI, which *"is a machine learning (ML) platform that lets you train and deploy ML models and AI applications, and customize large language models (LLMs) for use in your AI-powered applications."* (Google Cloud, 2024), but using a Docker-based Flask approach to deploy the model to an endpoint wasn't working after 2 days of trying to get it deployed, so the alternative was to export the model for use in the browser rather than server-side. Additional functionalities were implemented, such as fallback predictions using the OpenAI API and real-time vehicle pricing information through the eBay API. The web application also included features for user interaction and visualisation, ensuring a practical and engaging user experience.

3.5. Classification of the Conclusion

The conclusion was classified based on the effectiveness and practicality of the model and its integration into a user-friendly web application. A successful conclusion entailed the deployment of an accurate and efficient vehicle make-model-year classification model, accessible through a custom-made, nice-looking web app. This application not only provided predictions - but also offered additional value by integrating eBay listings for real-time vehicle pricing information. The documentation and public availability of the project on GitHub ensured reproducibility too, allowing for users to fork the project.

In summary, the methodology section provides a detailed account of the smart approach used to achieve the project's aims and objectives. By planning each step and using a range of tools

and technologies, the project successfully developed and deployed a robust image classification model for vehicle make-model-year identification.

4. Models & CNNs Context Literature

This section details the importance of using pre-trained models in the context of image classification, and provides an explanation of how certain pre-trained models, such as VGG16 and ResNet50, actually work in tandem with the concepts of a Convolutional Neural Network, and why they were useful to the assignment at hand. It's important to go over the inner-workings of each one to provide a greater understanding when dealing with the practical side of model tuning.

Pre-trained models are important in deep learning, mainly for tasks like image classification. These models are initially trained on extensive, MASSIVE datasets, such as ImageNet, which *“is an image database organized according to the WordNet hierarchy (currently only the nouns), in which each node of the hierarchy is depicted by hundreds and thousands of images [and] has been instrumental in advancing computer vision and deep learning research.”* As stated by (ImageNet, 2024). The pre-training process allows these models to learn a wide variety of features and patterns, which can then be transferred to other specific tasks through a process known as Transfer Learning. Transfer learning significantly reduces the computational resources and, more importantly for the assignment, time, required to train a model from scratch, as it uses the knowledge acquired during the initial training phase.

4.1. Convolutional Neural Networks

Before diving in to how the specific models used throughout the assignment work and detailing the importance, it's important to understand how CNNs work first, allowing for a better understanding of how the models utilise layers differently to help classify images.

A CNN is made up of several *“layers”*, each playing an important role in the *“feature”* extraction process. These layers (usually, depending on who is asked) include the *“convolutional layer, ReLU layer, pooling layer, and fully connected layer.”* (Huellman, 2022). But – what is a *“layer”*? As (Umair, 2020) puts it, *“The core building block of neural networks is the layer, a data-processing module that you can think of as a filter for data. Some data goes in, and it comes out in a more useful form. Specifically, layers extract representations out of the data fed into them”*. Essentially, each layer extracts important *“features”* from an image that helps, later, classify and learn what the image is when

presented with new data later on. More specifically, “A feature is a piece of data that is important for completing the computations necessary for a specific application. Features in an image can be particular elements like points, edges, or objects” as stated by (DrMax, 2024).

As per Figure 1, there is usually an input layer and an output layer, where the input layer deals the image data provided for training, and the output layer returns the probabilities of what the image is classified as. In between both, are the hidden layers, where the main processing happens.

Figure 1 - How CNN Classifies Image (Huellmann, 2022)

It’s important to note here that the problem at hand is a “multi-class” image classification problem, which is where “the defined classes allowed can be more than 2” as stated by (Shah & Sajjani, 2020). But what are “classes” (or “labels”, sometimes used interchangeably) and why can there be more than two? To put it in more simple terms, a class “is usually a discrete/Categorical variable” (Walia, 2017) that is trying to be predicted. For example, since the models used in this assignment have an end goal of being able to try and predict what “Make, Model, Year” a given car image is, a “class” would be “Nissan Juke 2021”, or “BMW M3 2024”. If someone was trying to train a model to predict what fruit is in an image, classes might be “Apple”, “Banana”, “Pear”, etc.

4.1.1. Convolution Layer

Convolutional layers are the most important part of a CNN. They use filters (also called kernels) that basically, in an abstract form, slide over the input image, performing multiplications with the input pixels and summing up the results. *“In mathematics (in particular, functional analysis), convolution is a mathematical operation on two functions (f and g) that produces a third function ($f * g$). The term convolution refers to both the result function and to the process of computing it”.* (Wikipedia, 2024). In Figure 2, it shows how convolution occurs on a 7x7 image, resulting in the feature map at the end.

Figure 2 - Convolution Operation on a 7x7 matrix with a 3x3 kernel (Basavarajaiah, 2019)

“The output is termed as the Feature map which gives us information about the image such as the corners and edges. Later, this feature map is fed to other layers to learn several other features of the input image.” (Gurucharan, 2022).

4.1.2. ReLU Layer

In its abstract form, ReLU, also known as the “rectified linear unit” layer, is to modify the feature map from the previous stage by turning any negative values in to ‘zeros’, mainly to create potential for discovering ‘non-linear’ patterns in images (through each layer thereafter). Before ReLU, in the convolution layer, multiplication is performed on the image with a kernel, creating the feature map that is passed to the ReLU layer. Since multiplication is a linear operation, this means that the output of the feature map is entirely linear and needs to be changed in some strategic way to ensure that non-linearity can be captured later on to identify more complex patterns in the image itself. If ReLU wasn’t in place, there would be a stronger focus on linear patterns, which isn’t how patterns in images are represented most of the time. ReLU is also quite performant relative to other “activation functions”, which are essentially a way to “decide whether a neuron should be activated or not. This means that it will decide whether the neuron’s input to the network is important or not in the process of prediction using simpler mathematical operations” (Baheti, 2021), like turning a negative value from the feature map (non-important) to a zero. As (Raghav, 2018) puts it, “There are other non linear functions such as tanh or sigmoid that can also be used instead of ReLU. Most of the data scientists use ReLU since performance wise ReLU is better than the other two.”. In Figure 3, a “Transfer Function”, which is just an Activation Function, is applied on to the feature map, in preparation for the next stage of a CNN. More complex patterns can now be found!

Figure 3 - ReLU Operation (Raghav, 2018)

4.1.3. Pooling Layer

Another key layer in a CNN is the Pooling Layer, which has a main focus on “*reducing the spatial dimensions of the input data, in terms of width and height, while retaining the most important information*” as (dremio, 2024) puts it. This essentially means, in an abstract form, reducing the complexity of images as well as the parameters to allow for, not only greater performance in calculations in further layers, but some regularisation too, which is “*a set of methods for reducing overfitting in machine learning models. Typically, regularization trades a marginal decrease in training accuracy for an increase in generalizability*” (Murel & Kavlakoglu, 2023), meaning that the model doesn’t “overlearn” the training data to which decreases the probability that the model performs better (makes better predictions) on unseen images, which happens due to removing data, instead of adding more focus on it.

In the Pooling Layer, a filter goes over the given input which does some kind of pooling function to create the output. Usually, “max-pooling” is done. “*It involves sliding a window (often called a filter or kernel) across the input data, similar to the convolution step, but instead of performing a matrix multiplication, max pooling takes the maximum value within the window. This maximum value becomes a single pixel in the new, pooled output*” (DeepAI, 2024), as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Max Pooling Application (Raghav, 2018)

4.1.4. Fully Connected Layer

Lastly, the “Fully Connected Layer” brings everything together, getting closer to the output layer. After the previous layers have extracted and simplified important features from the input data (like edges, shapes, and textures in an image, or door patterns, logos, window shapes, in cars, for example), the fully connected layer combines these features to make a final decision / prediction.

It's important to note that the Fully Connected Layer, although it may come closer to the end of the network, is not the “output layer”, as it doesn't give the absolute final predictions for each class using a softmax method. The output layer takes the information and features from the Fully Connected Layer and deals with the probabilities of predictions thereafter, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - CNN with Fully Connected Layer (developersbreach, 2024)

4.2. Pre-Trained Models

Pre-trained CNN models consist of a vast amount of multiple hidden layers, including convolutional layers for finding features, and fully connected layers for classification. These models are trained on extremely large datasets beforehand to learn rich feature representations, which can be fine-tuned for specific tasks with smaller datasets such as finding Make Model Year of vehicles. Below are explanations of how a few key models (used in assignment) work, and why they work efficiently.

4.2.1. ResNet50 Model

ResNet50, which stands for “Residual Network” made up of 50 CNN layers, is a powerful model that is not only efficient, but strategically accurate by being made up of multiple “residual blocks” as per Figure 6. These “residual blocks” are made up of a series of convolutional layers for extracting features, batch normalisation (which can “*stabilize the training process and improve the generalization ability of the model*” (DeepChecks, 2024)), activation functions, and “skip connections”, which “*are a type of shortcut that connects the output of one layer to the input of another layer that is not adjacent to it.*” (LinkedIn, 2024). Skip connections essentially preserve the input data and pass it to the last layer, skipping layers in between, which solves the vanishing gradient problem in non-shallow neural networks, such as ResNet50. It’s essentially added on as per Figure 7, where ‘x’ is the original information.

Figure 6 - ResNet50 Architecture (Kundu, 2023)

Figure 7 - Residual Block (Choudhary, 2023)

“ResNet50 has been trained on large datasets and achieves state-of-the-art results on several benchmarks. It has been trained on the ImageNet dataset, which contains over 14 million images and 1000 classes.” (Kundu, 2023). This brings a huge advantage to the assignment as transfer learning, as mentioned earlier, can come in to play here, meaning the entire ImageNet dataset doesn’t need to be retrained on since it has already been pre-trained, and layers near the end of the model can be tuned.

4.2.2. VGG16 Model

VGG16 is a relatively deep model made up of 16-weighted layers and uses 3x3 filters throughout the entire network. These 3x3 filters (kernels) essentially are scanned across the images producing a feature map, and it ends up improving the hierarchical learning and understanding of the image.

In VGG16, “VGG refers to the Visual Geometry Group of the University of Oxford, while the ‘16’ refers to the network’s 16 layers that have weights. This network is a pretty large network, and it has about 138 million parameters.” (Thakur, 2024). Although VGG16 has fewer layers than ResNet50, its simplicity and uniform design make it, in a way, somewhat easier to implement and train. VGG16 uses *consistent* 3x3 filters that effectively extract features throughout, and its straightforward structure is great for transfer learning as well.

As shown Figure 8, similar to ResNet50, the input starts off with 224x224x3 images (width, height and channels), so this makes it easier to implement when tuning the models and dealing with image preprocessing, especially considering multiple models are being tested.

VGG16 Architecture

Figure 8 - VGG16 Architecture (Rohini G, 2021)

“In VGG16 there are thirteen convolutional layers, five Max Pooling layers, and three Dense layers which sum up to 21 layers but it has only sixteen weight layers i.e., learnable parameters layer” (G, 2021).

4.2.3. VGG19 Model

Another important model to note, and one that was used briefly throughout the assignment when comparing models, was the VGG19 Model. VGG19, basically, is an extension of VGG16, featuring three additional convolutional layers, making it a much deeper network with a total of 19 layers. Both models use the same architecture pretty much, characterised by small 3x3 convolutional kernels, (same as VGG16) and max-pooling layers. The added depth in VGG19 allows it to learn more complex and detailed features from the input images, potentially leading to higher accuracy in classification. However, the increase in the amount of layers also means VGG19 requires more computational resources and longer training times compared to VGG16. Overall though, both models are highly effective for image recognition tasks and are widely used for transfer learning due to their performance and simplicity relative to ResNet50.

Figure 9 - VGG16 vs VGG19 (Ahmad, 2023)

5. Data Collection & Preprocessing

Collecting images involved sourcing a TON of images from different websites and manually sorting them into distinct classes, where a class represents a category or label that the model will learn to recognise, such as different makes and models of cars, and removing images that appeared as outliers. Each image needed to be carefully reviewed to ensure it was accurately labeled and appropriate for its given class, ensuring the dataset's integrity. Preprocessing these images was crucial because it standardises the input data, making sure all images are resized to the same dimensions. This step helps improve the model's ability to learn by providing uniform and high-quality data.

Considering there wasn't a good dataset available to use straight away, a custom dataset was collected. Initially, there was around 300 images per class, but, as overfitting seemed to appear, and abnormally high accuracy scores arose for both validation and training, around ~1100 images per class were later collected manually from many sources, resulting in lower accuracy scores (-10%), but no overfitting.

Below are the steps taken as well as an explanation of the preprocessing scripts used to get the images in the right state.

5.1. Data Collection

To begin, it was important to identify reliable sources for collecting images. As there is a high volume of car sales online, eBay was the first choice due to its comprehensive filters, allowing for precise searches of specific make, model, and year combinations. It also allowed for "real" images to be retrieved, taken from real sellers in different environments, allowing the model to be trained on more realistic data. Initially, images were sourced exclusively from eBay, resulting in about 300 images per class. However, this approach led to overfitting issues, so additional sources like Google, Shutterstock and AutoTrader were included. This expanded the dataset to approximately 1200 images per class, improving variety and model accuracy later down the road.

5.1.1. Defined Classes

The classes used for this project were:

- Audi-A3-2021
- Nissan-Qashqai-2021
- Ford-Fiesta-2015
- BMW-M3-2018
- Volkswagen-Golf-2017
- Vauxhall-Corsa-2021
- JUNK (to help with misclassification problems)

Obviously, in a more realistic sense, way more classes would be used, but consider this assignment as a proof of concept.

5.1.2. Scraping Process

Initially, custom web scraping attempts were made on eBay using Python. However, these efforts encountered persistent issues, with requests frequently timing out. This problem likely stemmed from eBay's automation detection mechanisms, which remained effective even after modifying scraping headers and settings. To overcome this obstacle, a more manual yet effective approach was adopted using a Chrome extension named "Download All Images." This extension, available at <https://download-all-images.mobilefirst.me/>, proved to be very valuable by locating and downloading ALL images from a webpage into a zip file, but this also caused some issues too..

While the extension excelled at bulk downloading, it also captured numerous irrelevant images, such as SVGs, profile pictures, and other non-vehicle-related visuals. Consequently, a large amount of manual effort was required to clean the dataset. This involved sifting through the downloaded images to remove any that were not apart of the specific class of vehicles. The manual cleaning process, though time-consuming, was essential to ensure the quality and relevance of the dataset. It took pretty much, around three hours to meticulously review, remove and deal with the images, ultimately resulting in a refined and more accurate collection of data for the assignment. This effort ensured that the dataset was free of irrelevant content, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the subsequent image classification tasks. Many interiors of cars, sample images, car parts and more had to be removed manually.

There was a thought down the line of using OpenAI’s GPT4V API (as GPT4-o wasn’t released as of that time) to deal with finding irrelevant images using a script, but this was most likely going to be expensive and time-consuming to create the script in the first place. It made sense here to go through things manually, but in a real-world project, maybe outsourcing, AI, and other means could be used to deal with sifting through images of a dataset.

5.1.3. Semi-Final Resulting Dataset

The semi-final dataset, after manually going through images, (*but not yet preprocessed via code*), is as follows in Table 1:

Table 1 - Manual Images Review Before Preprocessing

Class	Google	eBay	Shutterstock and/or AutoTrader	Images Before Manual Review	Images After Manual Review
Audi A3 2021	948 Images	515 Images	446 Images	1,909 Images	1146 Images
Nissan Qashqai 2021	677 Images	1097 Images	646 Images	2420 Images	1231 Images
Ford Fiesta 2015	1162 Images	1380 Images	0 Images	2542 Images	1336 Images
BMW M3 2018	760 Images	1734 Images	0 Images	2494 Images	1302 Images
Volkswagen Golf 2017	895 Images	953 Images	328 Images	2176 Images	1274 Images
Vauxhall Corsa 2021	940 Images	1407 Images	0 Images	2347 Images	1123 Images
Junk	2879 Images	0 Images	0 Images	2879 Images	2879 Images

5.2. Preprocessing

The next part, after manually going through the images in each class dataset, was to preprocess the data for each class, putting them in the correct size with the correct amount of channels, as well as removing duplicate photos via hashing.

5.2.1. File Structure

The preprocessing folder structure is designed to organise the image data efficiently and clearly. The root directory contains the Jupyter notebook file (Preprocessing.ipynb) which holds the code for processing the images. Additionally, it contains two main folders, which are “Manual_Check” and “Processed”. The folders in the “Processed” folder is the RESULT of running the script. Each folder representing a car contains images. The directory structure looks as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Preprocessing File Structure

5.2.2. Preprocessing.ipynb Script

To start things off, in the first part of the script in Figure 11, we import the necessary libraries: `os` for file handling, `PIL` for image processing, and `imagehash` for detecting duplicate images.

The image shows a Jupyter Notebook cell with a dark background. At the top left, there are three colored circles (red, yellow, green) followed by the text "AI2 - Preprocessing.ipynb". Below this, there is a list of 13 lines of Python code. The code imports the `os` module, `Image` from `PIL`, and `imagehash`. It then defines a list named `cars` containing six car models: "Audi-A3-2021", "Nissan-Qashqai-2021", "Ford-Fiesta-2015", "BMW-M3-2018", "Vauxhall-Corsa-2021", and "Volkswagen-Golf-2017", along with a "Z-Junk" category.

```
1 import os
2 from PIL import Image
3 import imagehash
4
5 # List of car classes to be processed
6 cars = [
7     "Audi-A3-2021",
8     "Nissan-Qashqai-2021",
9     "Ford-Fiesta-2015",
10    "BMW-M3-2018",
11    "Vauxhall-Corsa-2021",
12    "Volkswagen-Golf-2017", "Z-Junk"
13    ]
```

Figure 11 - Preprocessing Script / Part 1

Next, this block (Figure 12) defines a function called `process_images` that processes the images in the specified folder. It resizes the images to the correct size for VGG16 and ResNet50 and multiple other models unmentioned in the report, converts them to RGB, checks for duplicates using hashes, and saves the processed images in a new directory. Hashing is important here as it finds images with the exact same resulting hash and deletes the duplicate. Removing dupes is important as it could lead to overfitting in some way due to the model being trained too hard on one specific image.

```

AI2 - Preprocessing.ipynb

1 def process_images(source_folder, target_size=(224, 224)):
2     # Main directory for all processed images
3     main_processed_folder = "Processed"
4
5     # Ensure the main processed folder exists
6     if not os.path.exists(main_processed_folder):
7         os.makedirs(main_processed_folder)
8
9     # Define the destination folder within the main Processed folder
10    car_type = os.path.basename(source_folder) # Get the car folder name
11    dest_folder = os.path.join(main_processed_folder, f"{car_type}_Processed")
12
13    # Create the destination folder if it does not exist
14    if not os.path.exists(dest_folder):
15        os.makedirs(dest_folder)
16
17    # Initialize an image ID counter and hash dictionary for uniqueness and duplicate check
18    image_id = 0
19    hashes = {}
20
21    # Loop through all files in the source folder
22    for filename in os.listdir(source_folder):
23        if filename.lower().endswith(('.png', '.jpg', '.jpeg', '.webp')):
24            img_path = os.path.join(source_folder, filename)
25            try:
26                with Image.open(img_path) as img:
27                    # Convert the image to RGB mode and resize
28                    img = img.convert('RGB').resize(target_size)
29
30                    # Compute the hash of the image to check for duplicates
31                    img_hash = imagehash.average_hash(img)
32                    if img_hash in hashes:
33                        print(f"Duplicate found, skipping {filename} which is a duplicate of {hashes[img_hash]}")
34                        continue
35
36                    # Save the processed image
37                    new_filename = f"{image_id}.jpg"
38                    new_img_path = os.path.join(dest_folder, new_filename)
39                    img.save(new_img_path, 'JPEG')
40
41                    # Increment the image ID and store hash
42                    image_id += 1
43                    hashes[img_hash] = new_filename
44
45            except Exception as e:
46                print(f"Failed to process {filename}. Error: {e}")
47
48    print(f"Processed {image_id} unique images saved in {dest_folder}")

```

Figure 12 - Preprocessing Script / Part 2

Lastly, in Figure 13, the source folder is given and, for every single car inside of the source_folder (as well as junk), it is processed by calling the function from Part 2.


```
AI2 - Preprocessing.ipynb
1 # Process images for each car class
2 for car in cars:
3     source_folder = f"Manual_Check/{car}"
4     process_images(source_folder)
```

Figure 13 - Preprocessing Script / Part 3

5.2.3. Final Preprocessed Dataset

The table below (Table 2) shows before and after of the amount of images per class after preprocessing. Some manual removal and adjustment was done afterwards during tuning but only very few.

Table 2 - Final Preprocessed Resulting Dataset

Class	Images Before Preprocessing	Images After Preprocessing
Audi A3 2021	1146 Images	1030 Images
Nissan Qashqai 2021	1231 Images	1091 Images
Ford Fiesta 2015	1336 Images	1155 Images
BMW M3 2018	1302 Images	1209 Images
Volkswagen Golf 2017	1274 Images	1033 Images
Vauxhall Corsa 2021	1123 Images	982 Images
Junk	2879 Images	1265 Images

6. Model Implementation

The Model Implementation section details the various aspects and considerations involved in building and optimising the image classification model. This section is divided into three parts. The first part, Optimisers (and loss functions), explains the different optimisation algorithms used, including Adam, RMSprop, and SGD, and the Categorical Cross Entropy loss function discussing their mechanisms and the reasons for their selection during different stages of model development. The second part, TensorFlow Implementation, provides an in-depth look at the TensorFlow-based model architecture, processing steps, and training processes, showing the practical application of TensorFlow in this assignment. The third part, the Alternate PyTorch Implementation, describes the initial efforts to build the model using PyTorch, offering a comparative perspective and some pretty good insights gained from experimenting with another popular deep learning framework.

6.1. Optimisers & Loss Functions

As stated by (Aremu, 2022), “*An optimiser is a function or algorithm that is created and used for neural network attribute modification (i.e., weights, learning rates) for the purpose of speeding up convergence while minimizing loss and maximizing accuracy*”. The main goal is to minimise and reduce the loss function. “*A loss function is a function that compares the target and predicted output values; measures how well the neural network models the training data. When training, we aim to minimize this loss between the predicted and target outputs.*” (Yathish, 2022). The optimisers have an effect on reducing the loss efficiently, in the correct way to ensure accurate predictions. In regression, MSE (the Mean Squared Error) is used (as well as others), but, for this specific assignment, Categorical Cross-Entropy was used, as well as a few others.

6.1.1. Categorical Cross Entropy

In a general sense, Categorical Cross-Entropy works by applying a logarithm function to the probability assigned to the correct label, and providing a penalty to incorrect answers. With an example, it's like guessing 20% on BMW M3 2018 (when, in reality, it should be closer 100%). Assuming BMW M3 2018 is the correct guess for an image when the model is trying to learn, but the model is 20% confident, this means that the lower the confidence, the higher the penalty applied, meaning that if the model was 100% confident, there would be no

penalty, as it was actually the correct guess (label to image, BMW M3 2018 to the image of the BMW M3 2018). As (The 365 Team, 2023) puts it, “*The categorical cross-entropy loss function is commonly used in neural networks with softmax activation in the output layer for multi-class classification tasks. By minimizing loss, the model learns to assign higher probabilities to the correct class while reducing the probabilities for incorrect classes, improving accuracy*”. As a softmax activation function was used in this assignment, it made even more sense to use this in the final model with Tensorflow. It’s also worth nothing that one-hot-encoding was used too considering there is multiple classes and labels.

6.1.2. Adam

One of the first optimisers used in the assignment (but not in the final model) was the Adam optimiser, which is “*short for ‘Adaptive Moment Estimation,’ [and] is an iterative optimization algorithm used to minimize the loss function during the training of neural networks. Adam can be looked at as a combination of RMSprop and Stochastic Gradient Descent with momentum*” as stated by (Vishwakarma, 2024).

An extremely good explanation by Vishwakarma is shown below in Figure 14, as it easily describes how the Adam optimiser works in logical order.

1. **Start:** First, Adam sets up two things to keep track of how the network is doing. One is for the average (mean) of how steep the slope is when it’s figuring out how to improve (this is called the first moment). The other is for the average of how fast the slope is changing (this is called the second moment). Both start at zero.
2. **Look at the Slope:** During training, Adam checks how steep the slope is by looking at how the network’s guesses compare to the correct answers.
3. **Update the First Moment:** Adam then figures out the average slope over time. It’s like remembering how steep the hill has been in the past.
4. **Update the Second Moment:** Adam also figures out the average of how fast the slope is changing over time. This helps to understand if the slope is getting steeper or gentler.
5. **Correct the Bias:** At the beginning, since the averages start at zero, they might not be very accurate. So, Adam makes some adjustments to make them more accurate.
6. **Adjust the Parameters:** Finally, Adam uses these averages to help adjust the network’s settings a bit. It’s like gently nudging the network in the right direction to improve its performance.

By doing all of this, Adam helps the neural network learn more efficiently and effectively. It’s like having a good coach who guides the network to become better at its task.

Figure 14 - How Adam Works (Vishwakarma, 2024)

6.1.3. RMSprop

The final optimiser used for the assignment, the one which provided the most accurate results, was “RMSprop”, which *“is a gradient-based optimization technique used in training neural networks”* (Sanghvirajit, 2021), allows for an adaptive learning rate to be used efficiently in combination with a *“moving average of squared gradients to normalize the gradient. This normalization balances the step size (momentum), decreasing the step for large gradients to avoid exploding and increasing the step for small gradients to avoid vanishing”*. This means that, in abstract, the gradients (the errors, basically) are squared to create smoothness over the learning process, highlighting bigger errors more than small errors (as squaring impacts bigger numbers more than small, as well as making negative numbers positive). As (ChatGPT | (GPT4o), 2024) puts it (so take it with a grain of salt), *“Gradients can be noisy, especially in mini-batch gradient descent, where each batch might give slightly different gradients. By squaring the gradients and then taking a moving average, RMSprop smooths out this noise, focusing on the overall trend rather than individual fluctuations.”*

6.2. Tensorflow Implementation (FINAL MODEL)

To summarise, the code mounts Google Drive, sets up and initialises a pre-trained ResNet50 model, freezes its layers, and builds a new model with custom added layers. It loads, preprocesses, and augments training and validation datasets, then compiles and trains the model with class weights to handle imbalance. Finally, it saves the trained model, loads an image, and makes predictions, converting them to readable class names. Below is a detailed walkthrough of the code going through what each part does in detail for better understanding. This was the **FINAL** model used for the assignment.

To start things off, this code block in Figure 15 mounts the Google Drive into the Colab environment. This is essential for accessing files stored in Google Drive directly from the notebook. The `force_remount=True` parameter ensures that the drive is mounted even if it was already mounted before, refreshing the connection to the drive.

```
1 from google.colab import drive
2 drive.mount('/content/drive', force_remount=True)

Mounted at /content/drive
```

Figure 15 - Tensorflow Step 1

Next, (Figure 16) the ResNet50 model was imported from TensorFlow's Keras applications module, and the environment was set up for reproducibility by setting the random seeds for both numpy and Python's random module. The ResNet50 model is initialised with pre-trained weights from the ImageNet dataset, but the top classification layers are excluded (`include_top=False`). The input shape is defined as 224x224 pixels with 3 color channels (RGB) as is required by the model. It's worth noting here that other models were used such as VGG16, VGG19, etc, but, to make things more understandable, this script solely looks at the final ResNet50 script.

```

1  from tensorflow.keras.applications import ResNet50
2  import random
3  import numpy as np
4
5
6  np.random.seed(1)
7  random.seed(1)
8
9
10 model = ResNet50(weights='imagenet',
11                 include_top=False,
12                 input_shape=(224, 224, 3))

```

Figure 16 - Tensorflow Step 2

Next, this (Figure 17) loop iterates over all the layers of the ResNet50 model and sets their trainable attribute to False. This freezes the layers, meaning their weights will not be updated during training. This is a common practice in transfer learning to retain the learned features from the pre-trained model and only train the new layers added on top. If all layers were unfrozen, it would mean the entire model would have to be retrained – which would take forever and is not what is required.

```

1  for layer in model.layers:
2      layer.trainable = False

```

Figure 17 - Tensorflow Step 3

Next, this block (Figure 18) here defines a new sequential model, adding custom layers on top of the frozen ResNet50 model. The commented-out code shows a previous architecture attempt. The current model includes a GlobalAveragePooling2D layer to reduce the spatial dimensions of the input, followed by a dropout layer to prevent some overfitting that seemed to be happening earlier during tuning. A dense layer with 256 units and ReLU activation is

added, with L2 regularisation applied to prevent overfitting. Another dropout layer follows, and the final dense layer has 7 output units (7 classes of cars, basically) with softmax activation, corresponding to the number of classes. The regularisation factor was adjusted to 0.001 from an initial value of 0.0001.

```

1  from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
2  from tensorflow.keras.layers import *
3  from tensorflow.keras.regularizers import l2
4
5  # original model is commented out
6  # my_model = Sequential([model,
7  #                          GlobalAveragePooling2D(),
8  #                          Dropout(0.2),
9  #                          Dense(256, activation='relu'),
10 #                          Dropout(0.5),
11 #                          Dense(9, activation='softmax')])
12
13
14
15
16 regularization_factor = 0.001 # This is a hyperparameter that was originally set to 0.0001
17
18 my_model = Sequential([
19     model,
20     GlobalAveragePooling2D(),
21     Dropout(0.2),
22     Dense(256, activation='relu', kernel_regularizer=l2(regularization_factor)),
23     Dropout(0.5),
24     Dense(7, activation='softmax', kernel_regularizer=l2(regularization_factor))
25 ])

```

Figure 18 - Tensorflow Step 4

The next block (Figure 19) regards setting up datasets and doing some further preprocessing on the images. It's important to note here that there were 7 folders (each folder representing a MakeModelYear of car images) inside the AI2/Processed/ folder. The code sets up the training and validation datasets using `image_dataset_from_directory` from TensorFlow. The datasets are loaded from the specified directory, with images resized to 224 by 224 pixels. The datasets are split into training and validation subsets with a 30% validation split. The `shuffle=True` parameter shuffles the training dataset to ensure a good mix of data, while `shuffle=False` keeps the validation data order consistent. The `one_hot_encode` function is defined to convert the labels to one-hot encoding, which is then applied to both datasets using the map method. The `BATCH_SIZE` was also modified a lot during tuning, mainly from 8, to

16, to an eventual 32, which seemed to increase and decrease time to train and change accuracy. Most people online use 32, so it seemed like the best approach, even after tuning.

```
1  import tensorflow as tf
2
3  BATCH_SIZE = 32
4  SEED = 1
5
6  train_dataset = tf.keras.utils.image_dataset_from_directory(
7      '/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/Processed',
8      color_mode='rgb',
9      batch_size=BATCH_SIZE,
10     image_size=(224, 224),
11     shuffle=True,
12     validation_split=0.3,
13     subset='training',
14     seed=SEED)
15
16  val_dataset = tf.keras.utils.image_dataset_from_directory(
17     '/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/Processed',
18     color_mode='rgb',
19     batch_size=BATCH_SIZE,
20     image_size=(224, 224),
21     shuffle=False,
22     validation_split=0.3,
23     subset='validation',
24     seed=SEED
25 )
26
27  def one_hot_encode(image, label):
28     num_classes = 7 # using 7 classes
29     return image, tf.one_hot(label, num_classes)
30
31  train_dataset = train_dataset.map(one_hot_encode)
32  val_dataset = val_dataset.map(one_hot_encode)
33
```

```
Found 7331 files belonging to 7 classes.
Using 5132 files for training.
Found 7331 files belonging to 7 classes.
Using 2199 files for validation.
```

Figure 19 - Tensorflow Step 5

Next, this line (Figure 20) creates an iterator for the training dataset, which allows for manual iteration over the dataset. This is useful for examining the data and performing operations on individual batches, and allowed for some testing to be done to ensure that images were shown to be correctly dealt with.

```
1 iterator = iter(train_dataset)
```

Figure 20 - Tensorflow Step 6

This (Figure 21) retrieves the first image from the iterator and prints its shape as a numpy array. It just verifies that the images are correctly loaded and resized to the expected dimensions.

```
1 next(iterator)[0][0].numpy().shape  
  
(224, 224, 3)
```

Figure 21 - Tensorflow Step 7

This code snippet (Figure 22) visualises the first image in the training dataset iterator using Matplotlib. The image is converted to an integer type and displayed. This helps in inspecting the images being fed into the model to ensure they are correctly processed. It was clearly an image from the JUNK class as it was not an image of a car, but of a funny photo completely not related to the car dataset.

```
1 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
2
3 plt.imshow(next(iterator)[0][0].numpy().astype(np.int32))
```

<matplotlib.image.AxesImage at 0x7fd7f9090400>

Figure 22 - Tensorflow Step 8

This block (Figure 23) defines an augmentation function that randomly applies horizontal flipping, brightness adjustment, contrast adjustment, hue adjustment, and saturation adjustment to images. The function enhances the training dataset by creating variations of the images, improving the model's ability to generalise. The augmented dataset is concatenated with the original dataset to increase the dataset size. Augmentation is a very important step

used in Image Classification, especially if the dataset used is relatively small in size. Augmentation basically allows for slightly modified images (variations) to be used by applying certain effects on the dataset. It's almost similar to Feature Engineering in Linear Regression Models, where features can generate new, meaningful features – but not exactly.

```
1 from tensorflow.image import flip_left_right, adjust_brightness, adjust_contrast
2 from tensorflow.data import Dataset, AUTOTUNE
3 import tensorflow as tf
4
5 def augment(image, label):
6     # Random flip horizontally
7     image = tf.image.random_flip_left_right(image)
8
9     # Random brightness adjustment
10    image = tf.image.random_brightness(image, max_delta=0.2)
11
12    # Random contrast adjustment
13    image = tf.image.random_contrast(image, lower=0.8, upper=1.2)
14
15    # Apply color jitter
16    image = tf.image.random_hue(image, max_delta=0.04)
17    image = tf.image.random_saturation(image, lower=0.7, upper=1.3)
18
19    return image, label
20
21 # Apply augmentation only to the training dataset
22 train_dataset = train_dataset.map(augment, num_parallel_calls=AUTOTUNE)
23
24 # This augments with the original images included
25 train_dataset_augmented = train_dataset.map(augment, num_parallel_calls=AUTOTUNE)
26 train_dataset = train_dataset.concatenate(train_dataset_augmented)
27
28 # Prefetch to improve performance
29 train_dataset = train_dataset.prefetch(tf.data.AUTOTUNE)
```

Figure 23 - Tensorflow Step 9

This line (Figure 24) visualises another image from the training dataset iterator using Matplotlib, like the previous visualisation. It helped verify the data augmentation applied to the images.

Figure 24 - Tensorflow Step 10

Prefetching is then applied to the training dataset (Figure 25). Prefetching is used to improve performance by overlapping data preprocessing and model execution. As stated from (TensorFlow, 2024), “*Prefetching overlaps the preprocessing and model execution of a training step.*”.

```
1 train_dataset = train_dataset.prefetch(tf.data.AUTOTUNE)
2 train_dataset
```

Figure 25 - Tensorflow Step 11

Similarly, prefetching is also applied (Figure 26) to the validation dataset to improve performance during validation. This ensures that the validation data is efficiently fed into the model during evaluation.

```
1 val_dataset = val_dataset.prefetch(tf.data.AUTOTUNE)
2 val_dataset
```

Figure 26 - Tensorflow Step 12

Next, was to compile the model with the RMSprop optimiser (Figure 27), categorical crossentropy loss, and accuracy as a metric. RMSprop is chosen for its ability to handle non-stationary objectives and adjust the learning rate dynamically as mentioned in earlier chapters. The commented-out code shows the time-consuming previous attempts to compile the model using different optimisers like Adam and SGD, showing off here the experimentation done to find the best optimiser for the model. This took some time to figure out and tune.

```

1  from tensorflow.keras.metrics import *
2
3  from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import Adam, RMSprop, SGD
4  from tensorflow.keras.losses import CategoricalCrossentropy
5
6  my_model.compile(optimizer=RMSprop(learning_rate=0.001, rho=0.9),
7                  loss='categorical_crossentropy',
8                  metrics=['accuracy'])
9
10 # Old code is commented out here
11 # my_model.compile(optimizer=tf.keras.optimizers.Adam(learning_rate=0.001),
12 #                  loss='categorical_crossentropy',
13 #                  metrics=['accuracy'])
14
15 # from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import RMSprop
16
17 # Compile the model using RMSprop
18
19
20
21 # old code is commented out here
22 # my_model.compile(optimizer=SGD(learning_rate=0.001, momentum=0.9),
23 #                  loss='categorical_crossentropy',
24 #                  metrics=['accuracy'])
25
26

```

Figure 27 - Tensorflow Step 13

This block (Figure 28) calculates class weights to handle class imbalance. As (Teimourpour & Javaheri, 2014) puts it, “*The class imbalance problem typically occurs when there are many more instances of some classes than others. In such cases, standard classifiers tend to be overwhelmed by the large classes and ignore the small ones.*”. Labels from the training dataset are collected and converted from one-hot encoding to class indices. The `compute_class_weight` function from `sklearn` is used to calculate class weights, which are stored in a dictionary and printed. These weights can be used in the `fit` method of the model to give more importance to the smaller minority classes during training.

```

1 import numpy as np
2
3 from sklearn.utils.class_weight import compute_class_weight
4
5 # Initialize a list to store all labels
6 all_labels = []
7
8 # Iterate over the train_dataset to accumulate the labels
9 for images, labels in train_dataset:
10     # Convert one-hot encoded labels back to class indices and extend the list
11     all_labels.extend(tf.argmax(labels, axis=1).numpy())
12
13 # Calculate class frequencies and weights
14 class_weights = compute_class_weight(class_weight='balanced', classes=np.unique(all_labels), y=all_labels)
15 class_weights_dict = {i: weight for i, weight in enumerate(class_weights)}
16
17 # Use this dictionary in the fit function as class_weight
18 print(class_weights_dict)
19 print(class_weights)

```

```

{0: 1.0656146179401993, 1: 0.8655759824590994, 2: 0.9399267399267399, 3: 0.9596110695587136, 4: 1.0503479328694227, 5: 1.0098386462022826, 6: 1.1655689302748127}
[1.06561462 0.86557598 0.93992674 0.95961107 1.05034793 1.00983865
 1.16556893]

```

Figure 28 - Tensorflow Step 14

Next, the exciting part – actually training the model! This line (Figure 29) trains the model on the training dataset for 10 epochs, using the validation dataset for evaluation. The class weights calculated earlier are passed to handle class imbalance during training, ensuring that the model pays more attention to underrepresented classes. The epochs, class_weight, etc were tuned throughout, and it appears that 10 epochs was the best, as any further epochs caused the model to increase only very little relative to other increases from previous epochs, as well as sometimes decreasing too. As shown, it hit a relatively nice **accuracy** of around **80%**.

```

1 my_model.fit(train_dataset, epochs=10,
2             validation_data=val_dataset,
3             class_weight=class_weights_dict
4             )

```

```

Epoch 1/10
322/322 [=====] - 26s 69ms/step - loss: 1.5552 - accuracy: 0.5468 - val_loss: 0.9151 - val_accuracy: 0.7262
Epoch 2/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 66ms/step - loss: 1.0005 - accuracy: 0.7046 - val_loss: 0.5830 - val_accuracy: 0.8709
Epoch 3/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 66ms/step - loss: 0.8755 - accuracy: 0.7489 - val_loss: 0.4654 - val_accuracy: 0.9172
Epoch 4/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 66ms/step - loss: 0.8310 - accuracy: 0.7679 - val_loss: 0.4380 - val_accuracy: 0.9109
Epoch 5/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 67ms/step - loss: 0.7918 - accuracy: 0.7822 - val_loss: 0.3220 - val_accuracy: 0.9577
Epoch 6/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 67ms/step - loss: 0.7723 - accuracy: 0.7889 - val_loss: 0.5353 - val_accuracy: 0.8804
Epoch 7/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 67ms/step - loss: 0.7588 - accuracy: 0.7901 - val_loss: 0.4282 - val_accuracy: 0.9231
Epoch 8/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 67ms/step - loss: 0.7409 - accuracy: 0.7957 - val_loss: 0.4780 - val_accuracy: 0.8995
Epoch 9/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 67ms/step - loss: 0.7397 - accuracy: 0.7977 - val_loss: 0.3644 - val_accuracy: 0.9504
Epoch 10/10
322/322 [=====] - 22s 66ms/step - loss: 0.7300 - accuracy: 0.8006 - val_loss: 0.6213 - val_accuracy: 0.8458

```

Figure 29 - Tensorflow Step 15

After countless tuning attempts to get good accuracy, this block (Figure 30) saves the trained model to a specified path in Google Drive. Saving the model allows it to be loaded and used for predictions later in the web application, without the need to retrain it. The h5 format was used here as the package used to convert the h5 file in to a web-browser-allowed format didn't appear to work with other formats.

```
1 # save the trained model to be used with website later:
2
3 my_model.save('/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/ResNet50TF80.h5')
```

Figure 30 - Tensorflow Step 16

The next stage (Figure 31) was to test and see if predictions work. Only one is shown with one image, but multiple were used by replacing the import file string. This block opens an image from Google Drive using the PIL library and resizes it to 224 by 224 pixels, the input size expected by the model. Resizing ensures that the image dimensions match the input requirements of the trained model.

Figure 31 - Tensorflow Step 17

The image is converted (Figure 32) to a NumPy array, and its shape is printed to verify the dimensions. This conversion is necessary for feeding the image into the model for prediction.

```
1 img = np.asarray(image)
2
3 img.shape

(224, 224, 3)
```

Figure 32 - Tensorflow Step 18

This block (Figure 33) creates a deep copy of the image array and stores both the original and copied images in a list. The deepcopy function ensures that a completely separate copy of the image is made, not just a reference to the same data. When in colab, problems occurred when swapping images and this appeared to have resolved it. It also allowed for verification that the model can handle multiple images as input and produce CONSISTENT results.

```
1 from copy import deepcopy
2
3 img_2 = deepcopy(img)
4
5 images = [img, img_2]
```

Figure 33 - Tensorflow Step 19

The model predicts the classes of the images in the list (Figure 34). The predictions are printed to display the model's output probabilities for each class. This step demonstrates how to use the trained model to make predictions on new data in Python, even though the main goal was to do so in a web browser (which was achieved).

```

1 prediction = my_model.predict(np.array(images))
2
3 prediction

```

```
1/1 [=====] - 0s 29ms/step
```

```

array([[1.3191977e-02, 7.8251648e-01, 2.4305270e-03, 1.6880445e-01,
        4.1794251e-03, 2.8821714e-02, 5.5314158e-05],
       [1.3191977e-02, 7.8251648e-01, 2.4305270e-03, 1.6880445e-01,
        4.1794251e-03, 2.8821714e-02, 5.5314158e-05]], dtype=float32)

```

Figure 34 - Tensorflow Step 20

Lastly, this block (Figure 35) converts the model's output probabilities to class indices using `argmax`, maps these indices to class names, and prints the predicted classes for the images. The list of class names corresponds to the classes the model was trained to recognise, providing a human-readable interpretation of the model's predictions. The predictions were correct 😊!

```

1 class_indices = np.argmax(prediction, axis=1)
2
3 classes = sorted([
4     "Audi-A3-2021",
5     "Nissan-Qashqai-2021",
6     "Ford-Fiesta-2015",
7     "BMW-M3-2018",
8     "Vauxhall-Corsa-2021",
9     "Volkswagen-Golf-2017",
10    "Z-Junk"])
11
12 predicted_classes = [classes[index] for index in class_indices]
13
14 print(predicted_classes)

```

```
['BMW-M3-2018', 'BMW-M3-2018']
```

Figure 35 - Tensorflow Step 21

Overall, the model implementation appears to be quite efficient, but could potentially be improved in little ways, maybe readability more than anything – or reusability with functions, but it seemed right to make a sequentially readable notebook in this way.

The ResNet50 model gave an 80% accuracy score, and an 84% validation accuracy score. This is discussed more in the Results & Discussion section.

6.3. PyTorch *Alternate* Implementation

Before the Tensorflow approach was used, it felt right to use PyTorch instead purely out of curiosity. Below is a detailed approach to training another ResNet50 model, along with some different adjustments (such as different classes, 5, instead of 7), different augmentation, algorithms, etc. This is shown below for comparison purposes and more insight.

It's important to note that this PyTorch model implementation was NOT used, as the Tensorflow approach used a completely different dataset with way more images and better generalisation.

To start off, with PyTorch, (Figure 36) these imports were necessary, as well as ensuring that CUDAs were used (GPU) by explicitly stating to use them. The seeds were also set.


```
[1] import torch
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.optim as optim
from torchvision import transforms, datasets, models
from torch.utils.data import DataLoader, random_split, WeightedRandomSampler
from PIL import Image
import os
import numpy as np

torch.manual_seed(0) # Set the seed for reproducibility

# Directory containing the processed folders
data_dir = '/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/Processed'

device = torch.device('cuda' if torch.cuda.is_available() else 'cpu')

print(f'Using device: {device}')
```

Using device: cuda

Figure 36 - PyTorch Step 1

Next, this block (Figure 37) defines the image transformations for the training and test datasets. Training transformations include resizing, random horizontal flip, random rotation, colour jitter, conversion to tensor, and normalisation. Test transformations include resizing, conversion to tensor, and normalisation.

```

# Transformations for training and test datasets
train_transformations = transforms.Compose([
    transforms.Resize((224, 224)), # Resize all images to 224x224
    transforms.RandomHorizontalFlip(), # Data augmentation
    transforms.RandomRotation(15), # Data augmentation
    transforms.ColorJitter(), # Data augmentation
    transforms.ToTensor(),
    transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225])
])

test_transformations = transforms.Compose([
    transforms.Resize((224, 224)), # Resize all images to 224x224
    transforms.ToTensor(),
    transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225])
])

```

Figure 37 - PyTorch Step 2

Next, the code (Figure 38) loads the datasets using the defined transformations. Splits the training dataset into training and validation sets, using 70% for training and 30% for validation and prints the class names of the dataset. As shown, a different dataset was used.

```

# Load datasets with appropriate transformations
train_dataset = datasets.ImageFolder(root=data_dir, transform=train_transformations)
test_dataset = datasets.ImageFolder(root=data_dir, transform=test_transformations)

# Split the training dataset for training and validation
train_size = int(0.7 * len(train_dataset))
validation_size = len(train_dataset) - train_size
train_dataset, validation_dataset = random_split(train_dataset, [train_size, validation_size], generator=torch.Generator().manual_seed(0))

print(train_dataset.dataset.classes)

```

['Audi_A3_2021_Processed', 'BMW_1-Series_2016_Processed', 'Ford_Puma_2021_Processed', 'Nissan_Juke_2023_Processed', 'Nissan_Qashqai_2021_Processed']

Figure 38 - PyTorch Step 3

This part (Figure 39) calculates the class distribution in the training dataset. Creates weights inversely proportional to the class frequencies. Defines a weighted random sampler to handle class imbalance by giving more weight to less frequent classes, similar to the Tensorflow approach.

```

✓ 0s ▶ # Handle class imbalance
class_count = [0] * len(train_dataset.dataset.classes)
for _, index in train_dataset:
    class_count[index] += 1
weights = 1. / torch.tensor(class_count, dtype=torch.float)
sample_weights = weights[[label for _, label in train_dataset]]
sampler = WeightedRandomSampler(weights=sample_weights, num_samples=len(sample_weights))

```

Figure 39 - PyTorch Step 4

Figure 40 creates data loaders for training, validation, and test datasets. Uses the weighted random sampler for the training data loader to address class imbalance. Specifies batch sizes and shuffling for each loader.

```

✓ 0s ▶ # Data loaders
train_loader = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size=32, sampler)
validation_loader = DataLoader(validation_dataset, batch_size=16, shuffle=False)
test_loader = DataLoader(test_dataset, batch_size=16, shuffle=False)

```

Figure 40 - PyTorch Step 5

Figure 41 loads a pre-trained ResNet-50 model and freezes its parameters to prevent them from being updated during training. Replaces the final fully connected layer to match the number of classes in the dataset. Moves the model to the defined device. Defines the loss function (cross-entropy loss) and optimiser (Adam, a different one this time than TF) for training.

```
✓ [6] # Use a pre-trained model
3s net = models.resnet50(pretrained=True)
    for param in net.parameters():
        param.requires_grad = False # Freeze parameters of pre-trained model

    # Replace the last fully connected layer
    num_fts = net.fc.in_features
    net.fc = nn.Linear(num_fts, len(train_dataset.dataset.classes))

    # Move the model to the device
    net = net.to(device)

    # Loss function and optimizer
    criterion = nn.CrossEntropyLoss()
    optimizer = optim.Adam(net.fc.parameters(), lr=0.001)
```

Figure 41 - PyTorch Step 6

Figure 42 defines a function to train the model for a specified number of epochs. Iterates through the training data, computes the loss, performs backpropagation, and updates the model weights. Prints the training loss for each epoch. Validates the model after each epoch and prints the validation loss. Saves the model state after training.

```
[7] # Training the model
def train_model(num_epochs=10):
    net.train()
    for epoch in range(num_epochs):
        running_loss = 0.0
        for images, labels in train_loader:
            images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device)
            optimizer.zero_grad()
            outputs = net(images)
            loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
            loss.backward()
            optimizer.step()
            running_loss += loss.item()
        print(f'Epoch {epoch+1}, Loss: {running_loss / len(train_loader)}')

    # Validate the model
    validation_loss = 0.0
    net.eval()
    with torch.no_grad():
        for images, labels in validation_loader:
            images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device)
            outputs = net(images)
            loss = criterion(outputs, labels)
            validation_loss += loss.item()
        print(f'Validation Loss: {validation_loss / len(validation_loader)}')

    torch.save(net.state_dict(), '/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/model_state.pth')

train_model()
```

```
↔ Epoch 1, Loss: 1.5027619026325367
Validation Loss: 1.2420664973880933
Epoch 2, Loss: 1.06262516313129
Validation Loss: 0.9532908071642336
Epoch 3, Loss: 0.8418489429685805
Validation Loss: 0.863353210946788
Epoch 4, Loss: 0.7061239812109206
Validation Loss: 0.7349759703097136
Epoch 5, Loss: 0.6419331707336284
Validation Loss: 0.6277510782946711
Epoch 6, Loss: 0.5603082257288473
Validation Loss: 0.590560002171475
Epoch 7, Loss: 0.5753340367917661
Validation Loss: 0.6653988257698391
Epoch 8, Loss: 0.5085837167722208
Validation Loss: 0.5962053602156432
Epoch 9, Loss: 0.45204185997998275
Validation Loss: 0.5154637798019077
Epoch 10, Loss: 0.4390267034371694
Validation Loss: 0.5185343791609225
```

Figure 42 - PyTorch Step 7

Figure 43 defines a function to load the saved model state. Loads a pre-trained ResNet50 model, replaces the final fully connected layer, loads the saved state dictionary, moves the model to the defined device, and sets it to evaluation mode.

```

# Load the model function
def load_model():
    model = models.resnet50(pretrained=True)
    num_fters = model.fc.in_features
    model.fc = nn.Linear(num_fters, len(train_dataset.dataset.classes))
    model.load_state_dict(torch.load('/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/model_state.pth'))
    model = model.to(device)
    model.eval()
    return model

```

Figure 43 - PyTorch Step 8

Figure 44 defines a function to predict the class of a new image. Applies the necessary transformations to the image, converts it to a tensor, adds a batch dimension, and moves it to the defined device. Passes the image through the model to get the prediction and returns the predicted class name.

```

# Function to predict a new image
def predict_image(image_path, model):
    transform = transforms.Compose([
        transforms.Resize((224, 224)), # Resize the image to 224x224
        transforms.ToTensor(), # Convert image to tensor
        transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]) # Normalize
    ])
    image = Image.open(image_path).convert('RGB') # Open and ensure it's RGB
    image = transform(image) # Apply transformations
    image = image.unsqueeze(0).to(device) # Add batch dimension and send to device
    output = model(image) # Get the prediction from the model
    _, predicted = torch.max(output, 1) # Get the index of the maximum score
    class_index = predicted.item()
    return train_dataset.dataset.classes[class_index] # Return the class name

```

Figure 44 - PyTorch Step 9

Figure 45 creates and runs a function to evaluate the model on the test dataset. Loads the trained model, iterates through the test data, makes predictions, and compares them to the true labels. Calculates and prints the accuracy of the model on the test dataset. **This gave an ~88% Accuracy, better than Tensorflow, but is most likely overfit and unable to generalise as there is less data and no junk class (leading to more misclassification).**

```
✓ 8s ▶ # Evaluate the model on the test set
def evaluate_model():
    model = load_model()
    correct = 0
    total = 0
    with torch.no_grad():
        for images, labels in test_loader:
            images, labels = images.to(device), labels.to(device) # Move data to the device
            outputs = model(images)
            _, predicted = torch.max(outputs.data, 1)
            total += labels.size(0)
            correct += (predicted == labels).sum().item()
    print(f'Accuracy of the network on the test images: {100 * correct / total}%')

evaluate_model()

↔ Accuracy of the network on the test images: 87.99668874172185%
```

Figure 45 - PyTorch Step 10

Figure 46 uses the prediction function to predict the class of a new image. Prints the predicted class name for the specified image.

```
✓ 1s [11] dataClass = predict_image("/content/drive/MyDrive/AI2/RealTest/0.jpg", load_model())
      print(dataClass)

↔ Audi_A3_2021_Processed
```

Figure 46 - PyTorch Step 11

7. Results & Discussion

The assignment went through, in a very difficult and time-consuming manner, both PyTorch and TensorFlow implementations for training image classification models, comparing their performance and suitability. Initially, ResNet50 was implemented in PyTorch, followed by TensorFlow with additional models such as VGG16 and VGG19. The TensorFlow implementation was chosen as the final model due to its better handling of class imbalance, dataset augmentation, and overall performance, and more importantly, better generalisation.

In the PyTorch implementation, a pre-trained ResNet50 model was utilised, freezing its layers and adding a custom fully connected layer. Training transformations included resizing, data augmentation, and normalisation. **Despite achieving an accuracy of 88%**, the model potentially **suffered from overfitting** due to the smaller dataset and lack of a junk class, affecting its generalisation capability.

However, the TensorFlow implementation included strategic preprocessing, dataset augmentation, and better, faster handling of class imbalance through class weights. Different models (ResNet50, VGG16, VGG19) were experimented with, but ResNet50 was finalised for its (pretty good) balance between performance, readability, generalisability, and larger support online with better documentation (opinionated). **The TensorFlow model achieved 80% accuracy with better generalisation, attributed to a larger dataset and more diverse image augmentation techniques.**

Below details further analysis of the results of different models.

7.1. Final Model Results

Table 3 - Final Model Results

Model + Framework	Hyperparameters	Classes + Dataset Used	Accuracy (Metric)
ResNet50 with PyTorch	Torch seed: 0 Augment: Resize, RandomHFlip, Rotation, Jitter, Normalize Train Val Split: 70/30 Batch Size: 32, 32, 16 Cross-Entropy with Adam num_epochs: 10	5 Classes No Junk Class ~300 images per class ☹	Less Generalised, Most likely overfit with more misclassification. ~88%
ResNet50 with Tensorflow	Np + random seed: 1 No top All non-trainable layers for model Reg_factor: 0.001 Custom Layers: GAP2D, Dropout, Dense(reg + activation), Dropout, Dense(softmax) Batch Size: 32 Epochs: 10 Train Val Split: 70/30 Augment: RandomFlipLeftRight, RandomBrightness, RandomContrast, RandomHue, RandomSat Cross-Entropy with RMSprop	7 Classes Junk Class ~1000 images per class	More Generalised, way less misclassification! ☺ ~80% train ~85% val Best Model
VGG16 with Tensorflow	Np + random seed: 1 No top All non-trainable layers for model Train Val Split: 80/20 Reg_factor: 0.001 Custom Layers: GAP2D, Dropout, Dense(reg + activation), Dropout, Dense(softmax) Batch Size: 32 Epochs: 15 NO CLASS BALANCING	7 Classes Junk Class ~1000 images per class	Most likely overfit in some way and class balancing messing up validation accuracy. ~67% train ~93% val
VGG19 with Tensorflow	Np + random seed: 1 No top All non-trainable layers for model Reg_factor: 0.001 Custom Layers: GAP2D, Dropout, Dense(reg + activation), Dropout, Dense(softmax) Batch Size: 32 Epochs: 10 Train Val Split: 70/30 Augment: RandomFlipLeftRight, RandomBrightness, RandomContrast, RandomHue, RandomSat Cross-Entropy with RMSprop	7 Classes Junk Class ~1000 images per class	~75% train ~85% val

Overall, the final model that proved to be the best overall, considering the avoidance of misclassification and better generalisation overall – it has to go to the ResNet50 Model made with TensorFlow, with an accuracy of 80%.

8. Website Implementation

As mentioned in the Methodology, Next.js was used alongside many important open-source packages to get the ResNet50 TensorFlow model in to a position where it can be used on an actual website that allows for average price checks for a given car (from a given car image, to be more specific).

For those unaware of how a Next.js project works alongside react to create a functioning web application, it's not too crazy to wrap your head around. It's strongly recommended to watch a few videos and tutorials on how it works alongside React, but, considering this assignment revolves around AI, it's not too important to note the details here. It's mainly to display the EFFORT and TIME it took to not only build and tune a model, but utilise it in a way that ACTUALLY provides purpose in a nice-looking, fast user interface. It's certainly A+ worthy.

You can access the site now, for free, at <https://neurocar.net>.

8.1. Directory Structure

Below, is the listed directory structure for the web application, featuring many components, api routes, middleware, config files, model files, etc.

Structure:**app**

```

├── api
│   ├── getEbay
│   │   └── route.tsx
│   ├── predictImage
│   │   └── route.tsx
│   ├── error.tsx
│   ├── layout.tsx
│   ├── page.tsx
│   └── providers.tsx
├── components
│   ├── TransitionContentUtils
│   │   ├── useTransitionContent.ts
│   │   └── TransitionWrapper.tsx
│   ├── cn.ts
│   ├── DragDropBox.tsx
│   ├── DragDropPage.tsx
│   └── ... more components

```

config**node_modules****public**

```

├── fonts
│   └── ...
├── models
│   ├── group1-shard1of23.bin
│   ├── ... more bin files
│   └── model.json
├── bg-grad-2.svg
├── bg3.png
└── favicon.ico

```

styles**middleware.ts****next.config.js****package.json****postcss.config.js****tailwind.config.js****tsconfig.json**

8.2. Explanation & Implementation

The Next.js project leverages the power of React to build a highly scalable, server-side rendered application while using Vercel to host. At its foundation, it organises functionality through the **app/** directory, where **api/** contains route handlers for backend operations like fetching eBay data and predicting car details using **OpenAI's API**. The **components/** directory hosts reusable UI components and utilities such as drag-and-drop functionality, loading indicators, and multi step processes. Key components like `layout.tsx` and `providers.tsx` set up global styles, metadata, and context providers, ensuring consistent theming and state management across the app. The **public/** directory holds static assets accessible to the client, including images and **TensorFlow.js model files** used for in-browser machine learning tasks. Configurations and settings are managed through files in the **config/**, **styles/**, and **types/** directories, along with root-level files like `.env.development.local` for environment variables, `middleware.ts` for request handling, and other config files for ESLint, Tailwind CSS, and TypeScript. This structured approach allows for clean code organisation, efficient state management, and seamless integration of server-side and client-side logic, giving a very nice framework for building modern web apps.

8.2.1. TensorFlow .h5 Conversion

This Next.js project integrates machine learning by converting a pre-trained Keras model (.h5 format) into a format usable by TensorFlow.js in the web browser. The conversion is accomplished using the `tensorflowjs_converter` command, which transforms the Keras model into a set of binary shard files and a `model.json` file. These files are placed in the `public/models/` directory. When the application loads, the TensorFlow.js library (`tf.js`) can directly load these converted files into the browser, enabling in-browser predictions. The command converts the ResNet50 model from Keras's H5 format to TensorFlow.js format, generating shard files (`group1-shard1of23.bin` to `group1-shard23of23.bin`) and a `model.json` file that contain the model's architecture and weights. This allows the Next.js app to use the model **DIRECTLY** in the browser, client-side, providing functionalities like image recognition and prediction without needing server-side computations! (Doing it with Flask and trying to deploy to Vertex AI was a nightmare – this approach was much easier)

The command is as follows as shown in Figure 47.

```
base ~  
tensorflowjs_converter --input_format keras /Users/brandonhaynes/  
Desktop/resnet/ResNet50TF80.h5 /Users/brandonhaynes/Desktop/  
resnet/model
```

Figure 47 - Tensorflowjs_converter command

This (Figure 48) produces a folder of the following files (which are ALL added to the /public/models/ directory in the web application):

Figure 48 - Tensorflowjs_converter Output

8.2.2. Loading Model Client-Side in Browser

This code (Figure 49) is responsible for loading the ResNet50 model. The model is either fetched from a URL (which is linked to the /public directory basically, commonly seen in a lot of traditional web apps) or loaded from the browser's IndexedDB storage if it has been previously cached there. This caching mechanism helps optimise the loading time by avoiding repeated downloads of the model, especially considering its very large. It's storing the model in local state 'model', and, once the model is loaded, it calls navigateTo() to change the UI (like a sub page inside the main page), getting out of the 'loading' page into the 'main' page where a user can drag and drop images. This is all achieved inside a useEffect() hook, which runs after the component (the page itself) is mounted, only once.

```
ai2 - page.tsx
46 const { currentPage, navigateTo, navigateBack } = useTransitionContent('loading');
47
48 const [model, setModel] = React.useState<any>(null);
49 const { state, dispatch } = useMyContext();
50
51 useEffect(() => {
52   async function loadModel() {
53     const url = '/models/model.json';
54     const modelName = 'my-model';
55
56     // Check if the model is already in IndexedDB.
57     const modelExists = await tf.io.listModels();
58     // check if dictionary is empty
59
60     if (Object.keys(modelExists).length !== 0) {
61       console.log('Models in IndexedDB:', modelExists);
62       // If it's in IndexedDB, use the cached model.
63       const model = await tf.loadLayersModel(`indexeddb://${modelName}`);
64       setModel(model);
65       navigateTo('main');
66     } else {
67       // If it's not in IndexedDB, fetch it.
68       const model = await tf.loadLayersModel(url);
69
70       // Save the model to IndexedDB for future use.
71       await model.save(`indexeddb://${modelName}`);
72
73       setModel(model);
74       navigateTo('main');
75     }
76   }
77
78   loadModel();
79 }, []);
```

Figure 49 - Downloading & Caching Model

8.2.3. Making Predictions

This code (Figure 50) makes the prediction of car make, model, and year using TensorFlow.js (tfjs). It begins by checking if there are image files in the global state, and if any vehicle details have already been set. If no image files are present or if vehicle details are already defined, the function exits early. If there are image files and no vehicle details, it navigates to the 'predictingLoading' page, showing that a prediction process is underway.

The main prediction logic is encapsulated within an async function `newImgFunc`. This function creates a new image object and assigns its source to the first image file from the state. Once the image is fully loaded, the function proceeds to convert the image into a tensor format using `tf.browser.fromPixels(img)`, which is then resized to 224 by 224 pixels using bilinear interpolation. This resized tensor is the expected input format for the model.

The tensor is then fed into the prediction model by calling `model.predict(tensor.expandDims())`, which outputs an array of probabilities for each class. These classes represent different car models as well as a "Junk" category, indicating an unidentifiable object. The prediction results are retrieved using `prediction.dataSync()`, and the highest probability value (`maxPrediction`) is determined. The index of this highest value (`predictedClassIndex`) indicates the predicted class.

If the predicted class corresponds to the "Junk" category (index 6) or if the highest probability is below a confidence threshold of 0.75, the function logs that the model is not confident in its prediction. It then calls the OpenAI API to find out what the image is (`callPredictAPI(img)`) for further analysis. This external call serves as a **fallback mechanism** to handle cases where the model's confidence is insufficient, ensuring that the website can still provide meaningful predictions.

For predictions where the model's confidence exceeds the threshold and the class is not "Junk", the function maps the predicted class index to specific car details (make, model, and year) using predefined arrays. These details are then dispatched to the global state using the dispatch function (`context`), updating the state with the predicted vehicle details.

```

ai2 - page.tsx

191 useEffect(() => {
192   if (!state.imageFiles) return;
193   if (state.imageFiles.length === 0) return;
194   if (state.vehicleDetails.make) return;
195
196   navigateTo('predictingLoading');
197
198   const newImgFunc = async () => {
199     const img = new Image();
200     const imageFile = state.imageFiles[0];
201
202     img.src = URL.createObjectURL(imageFile);
203
204     img.onload = async () => {
205       const class_names = [
206         'Audi-A3-2021',
207         'BMW-M3-2018',
208         'Ford-Fiesta-2015',
209         'Nissan-Qashqai-2021',
210         'Vauxhall-Corsa-2021',
211         'Volkswagen-Golf-2017',
212         'Z-Junk']
213       const class_names_mmy = [
214         {
215           make: 'Audi',
216           model: 'A3',
217           year: '2021',
218         },
219         // ...
220         // ...
221       ]
222
223       let tensor = tf.browser.fromPixels(img).resizeBilinear([224, 224])
224       const threshold = 0.75;
225
226       const prediction = await model.predict(tensor.expandDims());
227       const predictions = prediction.dataSync();
228       console.log('Predictions:', predictions);
229       const maxPrediction = Math.max(...predictions);
230       const predictedClassIndex = predictions.indexOf(maxPrediction);
231
232       if (predictedClassIndex === 6) {
233         await callPredictAPI(img);
234       }
235       else {
236         if (maxPrediction < threshold) {
237           console.log('The model is not confident in its prediction.');
```

Figure 50 - Tfjs Prediction

To put that in more simple terms, the below diagram (Figure 51) was made to display the order of events.

Figure 51 - Prediction Flowchart

8.2.4. OpenAI Fallback API

It was a strategic move here to implement some kind of “AI” feature in to the web application apart from the custom made model, as it provided some ***MAGIC*** to the application. The point of calling OpenAI’s GPT4o API (inside a custom Next.js Route Handler) was to try and identify a car’s make model and year using GPT’s Vision capability, as well as identify if it’s actually a car and not a different image. It works surprisingly well!

The POST function begins (Figure 52) by importing necessary modules from next/server, as well as the OpenAI library. The OpenAI API is initialised with an API key stored in environment variables. This setup allows the API to communicate securely with OpenAI’s servers. The function then attempts to parse the incoming request’s JSON body, while nicely handling any errors that occur during this process. If the JSON parsing fails or if the required image field is missing from the request, the function responds with a 401 status code and an appropriate error message. This ensures that only valid requests with the necessary data proceed further.


```
ai2 - route.tsx

3 import { NextRequest, NextResponse } from "next/server";
4 import OpenAI from 'openai';
5
6 export async function POST(request: NextRequest, response: NextResponse) {
7
8     const openai = new OpenAI({
9         apiKey: process.env['OPENAI_API_KEY'],
10    });
11
12
13    let data;
14    try {
15        data = await request.json()
16    }
17    catch (error) {
18        console.log(error)
19        return NextResponse.json({}, { status: 401 });
20    }
21
22    if (!data.image) {
23        return NextResponse.json({
24            error: "No image provided"
25        }, { status: 401 });
26    }
27 }
```

Figure 52 - /api/predictImage Part 1

In this part (Figure 53), the function creates a request to OpenAI's API to analyse the provided image. The request specifies a model (defaulting to "gpt-4o" if not provided in environment variables) and the desired response format. The messages array contains a detailed instruction (prompt) for the API, explaining that it should analyse the image and return specific details about the car, such as make, model, year, and other attributes, in JSON format. The image URL (base64 encoded client-side) is included in the message content. Once the request is set up, it is sent to OpenAI's servers. If the response from OpenAI does not contain the expected content, the function responds with a 401 status code and an error message, ensuring that only successful and valid responses are processed further.

```
ai2 - route.tsx

30 const responseAi = await openai.chat.completions.create({
31   model: process.env['OPENAI_API_MODEL'] as any ?? "gpt-4o",
32   response_format: { type: "json_object" },
33   messages: [
34     {
35       role: "user",
36       content: [
37         { type: "text", text: `You are a helpful assistant designed to output JSON
38           and identify what car is in images and to give details back about the given
39           car in a strict json format. You will give back JSON with the following keys:
40           make, model, year, description, colour, is_vehicle, confidence_in_mmy.
41           The is_vehicle attribute should be true or false depending if the image is actually
42           of a vehicle that is meant to be on road, such as a car bike van etc, and its a real
43           life vehicle, not fictional. The confidence_in_mmy should be a value between 0 and 1
44           indicating how confident you are with the given make model year. If you can't identify
45           a make model year, make the values you cant find null. What's in this image?` },
46         {
47           type: "image_url",
48           image_url: {
49             "url": data.image,
50           },
51         },
52       ],
53     },
54   ],
55 });
56
57 if (!responseAi.choices[0].message.content) {
58   return NextResponse.json({
59     error: "No response from AI"
60   }, { status: 401 });
61 }
```

Figure 53 - /api/predictImage Part 2

Lastly, in the final part (Figure 54), the function attempts to parse the JSON content from OpenAI's response. If this parsing fails, the function catches the error and responds with a 401 status code and an error message, indicating that there was an issue processing the response. If the parsing is successful, the parsed JSON object, which contains the predicted details of the car, is returned to the client with a 200 status code. This ensures that the client receives the data in a structured format, ready for use in the application's front-end.

A screenshot of a code editor window titled "ai2 - route.tsx". The code is written in TypeScript and shows a try-catch block. Line 57 starts with "try {". Line 58 has "const toJson = JSON.parse(responseAi.choices[0].message.content)". Line 59 is empty. Line 60 has "return NextResponse.json({ outputFromModel: toJson }, { status: 200 });". Line 61 is empty. Line 62 has "} catch (error) {". Line 63 has "console.log(error)". Line 64 has "return NextResponse.json({". Line 65 has "error: 'Error parsing AI response'". Line 66 has "}, { status: 401 });". Line 67 has "}".

```
57 try {
58   const toJson = JSON.parse(responseAi.choices[0].message.content)
59
60   return NextResponse.json({ outputFromModel: toJson }, { status: 200 });
61
62 } catch (error) {
63   console.log(error)
64   return NextResponse.json({
65     error: "Error parsing AI response"
66   }, { status: 401 });
67 }
```

Figure 54 - /api/predictImage Part 3

Now that the API route (Next.js Route Handler) is defined and can be called via /api/predictImage, it can be used in the front-end (page.tsx, which links to '/' or the index page) as shown below.

The callPredictAPI function starts (Figure 55) by preparing the image for analysis. It creates an HTML canvas element, sets its dimensions to match the uploaded image, and draws the image onto the canvas. This process allows the function to convert the image into a different format which is required for OpenAI's API. The canvas content is then converted into a JPEG format and encoded as a Base64 string using the toDataURL method. This Base64 string representation of the image (jpgUrl) is used as the payload for the API request. The function sends a POST request to the /api/predictImage endpoint, including the image data in the request body.


```

82  const callPredictAPI = async (img: any) => {
83
84    const canvas = document.createElement('canvas');
85    canvas.width = img.width;
86    canvas.height = img.height;
87    const ctx = canvas.getContext('2d');
88    // @ts-ignore
89    ctx.drawImage(img, 0, 0);
90
91    // Convert the canvas image to JPG format
92    const jpgUrl = canvas.toDataURL('image/jpeg');
93
94    // The jpgUrl is a base64 string of the image in JPG format
95
96    const response = await fetch('/api/predictImage', {
97      method: 'POST',
98      headers: {
99        'Content-Type': 'application/json',
100     },
101     body: JSON.stringify({ image: jpgUrl }),
102   });

```

Figure 55 - callPredictAPI Client-Side Part 1

Once the POST request is sent, the function checks the response status (Figure 56). If the response is not successful (status not OK), it sets a timeout to navigate back to the main screen after one second. This timeout handles different error scenarios. For a 429 status code (rate limit exceeded), it parses the reset time from the response and calculates how long the user should wait before trying again, displaying this information using a toast. And yes – rate limiting was implemented for the API routes just in case a user decides to be dumb and use all the OpenAI credits (money). For a 500 status code (server error), it displays an error message from the response. Regardless of the specific error, the function resets the application state by dispatching SET_ALL_NULL and navigates back to the main screen.

```

ai2 - page.tsx

104  if (!response.ok) {
105    setTimeout(async () => {
106
107      if (response.status === 429) {
108        const responseBody = await response.json();
109        const resetTime = responseBody.reset;
110        // Check if resetTime is a valid number
111        if (!resetTime) {
112          toast.error('Error. Please try again later.');
```

Figure 56 - callPredictAPI Client-Side Part 2

If the API response is successful, the function (Figure 57) parses the JSON data returned by the server. It checks for errors in the response and validates the presence of the outputFromModel field, which contains the AI-predicted car details. If the field is missing or indicates that the image is not a vehicle, appropriate error messages are shown using toast notifications, and the function navigates back to the main screen. If OpenAI's API successfully ID's the vehicle and gives the make, model, and year, these details are dispatched to the global state with the action SET_VEHICLE_DETAILS. This updates the application's state with the new vehicle information, enabling the next step to occur where the user can confirm and/or change the info to, eventually, get the average price of the vehicle.

```
ai2 - page.tsx

145   const data = await response.json();
146
147   if (data.error) {
148     toast.error(data.error);
149     navigateTo('main');
150     return;
151   }
152
153
154   if (!data.outputFromModel) {
155     toast.error('Failed to predict the image');
156     navigateTo('main');
157     return;
158   }
159
160   const dataFromModel = data.outputFromModel;
161
162   if (dataFromModel.is_vehicle === false) {
163     toast.error('This is not a vehicle. Please upload an image of a vehicle.');
```

```
164     navigateTo('main');
165     return;
166   }
167
168
169   if (!dataFromModel.make && !dataFromModel.model && !dataFromModel.year) {
170     toast.error('Failed to predict the image');
171     navigateTo('main');
172     return;
173   }
174
175   dispatch({type: 'SET_VEHICLE_DETAILS',
176     payload: {
177       ...state.vehicleDetails,
178       make: dataFromModel.make,
179       model: dataFromModel.model,
180       year: dataFromModel.year
181     }});
182   };
```

Figure 57 - callPredictAPI Client-Side Part 3

8.2.5. eBay API

Next, after the vehicle Make Model and Year has been identified and confirmed by the user, an average price of the vehicle needs to be retrieved somehow, as well as supported listings from eBay to give the user some flexibility to see the prices for themselves that helped in calculating said average.

The average vehicle price is, essentially, calculated by pulling eBay listings for the given car using eBay's API (which has absolutely horrendous and outdated documentation, by the way, a nightmare of an API to use), and then simply averaging the price of all listings. (all listing prices / amount of listings).

The POST function starts off (Figure 58) by importing next/server module (again) and ebay-api. It initialises the eBay API client using credentials stored in environment variables, which are used for authenticating API requests to eBay. The function then attempts to parse the incoming JSON, handling any errors that occur. If JSON parsing fails or if the required carDetails field is missing from the request, the function responds with a 401 status code and an appropriate error message. This ensures that only valid requests with the necessary car details proceed further.

```

ai2 - route.tsx

2  import { NextRequest, NextResponse } from "next/server";
3  import eBayApi from 'ebay-api';
4
5  export async function POST(request: NextRequest, response: NextResponse) {
6      const eBay = new eBayApi({
7          appId: process.env.EBAY_APP_ID as any,
8          certId: process.env.EBAY_CERT_ID as any,
9          sandbox: false,
10         siteId: eBayApi.SiteId.EBAY_GB,
11         marketplaceId: eBayApi.MarketplaceId.EBAY_GB,
12     });
13
14     let data;
15     try {
16         data = await request.json()
17     }
18     catch (error) {
19         console.log(error)
20         return NextResponse.json({}, { status: 401 });
21     }
22
23     if (!data.carDetails) {
24         console.log("No carDetails provided")
25         return NextResponse.json({
26             error: "No carDetails provided"
27         }, { status: 401 });
28     }
29
30     const { make, model, year } = data.carDetails;
31
32     if (!make && !model && !year) {
33         console.log("Make, Model and Year are missing")
34         return NextResponse.json({
35             error: "Make, Model and Year are missing"
36         }, { status: 401 });
37     }

```

Figure 58 - /api/getEbay Part 1

In this section of the code (Figure 59), the function constructs filters and keywords for the eBay query based on the provided car details (make, model, and year). It populates arrays for item filters and aspect filters, and constructs a keyword string to refine the search. This took some time to figure out what everything meant considering eBay's API SUCKS. These filters and keywords are used to query eBay's database for relevant car listings. The function then

sends a request to eBay's Finding API, specifying site and marketplace IDs, pagination parameters, category ID for vehicles, and the constructed keywords. The API request includes necessary headers for authentication. This query aims to find up to 100 listings of vehicles matching the provided details.

```
ai2 - route.tsx

39  const itemFilter = [];
40  const aspectFilter = [];
41  let keywords = '';
42
43  if (make) {
44    itemFilter.push({ name: 'Manufacturer', value: make });
45    aspectFilter.push({ aspectName: 'Manufacturer', aspectValueName: make });
46    keywords += make + ' ';
47  }
48
49  if (model) {
50    itemFilter.push({ name: 'Model', value: model });
51    aspectFilter.push({ aspectName: 'Model', aspectValueName: model });
52    keywords += model + ' ';
53  }
54
55  if (year) {
56    itemFilter.push({ name: 'Model Year', value: year });
57    aspectFilter.push({ aspectName: 'Model Year', aspectValueName: year });
58    keywords += year;
59  }
60
61  const ebayResponse = await eBay.finding.findItemsAdvanced({
62    siteId: eBayApi.SiteId.EBAY_GB,
63    marketplaceId: eBayApi.MarketplaceId.EBAY_GB,
64    paginationInput: {
65      entriesPerPage: 100,
66      pageNumber: 1
67    },
68    categoryId: '9800',
69    keywords
70  }, {
71    headers: {
72      'X-EBAY-SOA-GLOBAL-ID': 'EBAY-GB',
73    }
74  });
```

Figure 59 - /api/getEbay Part 2

After receiving the response from eBay, the function (Figure 60) checks if any items were found. If no items are found, it responds with a 401 status code and an appropriate error message. If items are found, it iterates through the listings to calculate the total price and compile a list of item details. For each listing, it extracts relevant information such as item ID, title, condition, location, price, URL, and image, and adds these to an array of final items. After processing all items, the function calculates the average price of the listed vehicles by dividing the total price by the number of items. It then constructs a response object containing the average price and the list of items, which is returned to the client with a 200 status code. This enables the client to display both the average vehicle price and detailed information about the listings used to calculate that average, providing purpose to the website ☺.

```

ai2 - route.tsx
76   const items = ebayResponse.searchResult.item;
77
78   if (!items) {
79     console.log("No items found")
80     return NextResponse.json({
81       error: "No items found"
82     }, { status: 401 });
83   }
84   let sumPrices = 0;
85   const finalItems: { id: any, title: any, price: any, url: any, image: any, condition: any, location: any }[] = [];
86
87   items.forEach((item: any) => {
88     sumPrices += item.sellingStatus.currentPrice.value;
89     try {
90       finalItems.push({
91         id: item.itemId,
92         title: item.title,
93         condition: item?.condition?.conditionDisplayName || 'N/A',
94         location: item.location || 'N/A',
95         price: item.sellingStatus.currentPrice.value,
96         url: item.viewItemURL,
97         image: item.galleryURL
98       });
99     }
100    catch (error) {
101      console.log(error)
102    }
103  });
104
105  if (finalItems.length === 0) {
106    console.log("No items found")
107    return NextResponse.json({
108      error: "No items found"
109    }, { status: 401 });
110  }
111
112  const ebayReturnResponse = {
113    averagePrice: sumPrices / items.length,
114    items: finalItems
115  }
116
117  return NextResponse.json({ ebayReturnResponse }, { status: 200 });
118 }
119

```

Figure 60 - /api/getEbay Part 3

8.2.6. Middleware Rate Limiting

Before any requests are made to the /api routes, to deal with setup as well as preventing abuse, the following middleware was implemented.

The middleware begins (Figure 61) by importing the modules from next/server and initialising a rate limiter using upstash/ratelimit and Vercel's kv store for Redis. The Ratelimit instance is configured to allow a maximum of 3 requests from the same IP within 180 seconds. This setup helps in preventing abuse (which is highly unlikely as this is for an assignment, but it's good practice and it's key to go above and beyond) and ensuring fair usage of the third-party API resources. The config object defines which routes the rate limiter should apply to, specifically targeting all routes under the /api path. This configuration ensures that any requests to these routes will be subject to the rate limiting rules defined.


```
ai2 - middleware.ts

1 import { NextRequest, NextResponse } from 'next/server';
2 import { Ratelimit } from '@upstash/ratelimit';
3 import { kv } from '@vercel/kv';
4
5 const ratelimit = new Ratelimit({
6   redis: kv,
7   // 3 requests from the same IP in 180 seconds
8   limiter: Ratelimit.slidingWindow(3, '180 s'),
9 });
10
11 // Define which routes to rate limit
12 export const config = {
13   matcher: ['/api/:path*'], // This matches all routes under /api
14 };
```

Figure 61 - Middleware Part 1

The middleware func is an async function (Figure 62) that first checks for the presence of MANDATORY environment variables needed for the application to function correctly. These variables include API keys and tokens for OpenAI, Vercel KV, and eBay. If any required environment variables are missing, the function returns a 500 status response with an error message listing the missing variables. This validation ensures that all necessary configurations are in place before processing any requests.

The middleware then checks the current environment. If the environment is not production (e.g., development or staging), the function bypasses the rate limiting and proceeds to the next middleware or route handler using `NextResponse.next()`. This allows for unrestricted access during development and testing.

For production environments, the middleware retrieves the client's IP address and checks it against the rate limiter. If the rate limit is not exceeded, the request proceeds normally. If the rate limit is exceeded, the middleware responds with a 429 status code and an error message, indicating that the rate limit has been reached. This response includes information about the limit, remaining requests, and reset time, providing the client with details about the rate limiting status.

```
ai2 - middleware.ts
16 export default async function middleware(request: NextRequest) {
17
18   const requiredEnvVars = [
19     'OPENAI_API_KEY',
20     'OPENAI_API_MODEL',
21     'KV_URL',
22     'KV_REST_API_URL',
23     'KV_REST_API_TOKEN',
24     'KV_REST_API_READ_ONLY_TOKEN',
25     'EBAY_APP_ID',
26     'EBAY_CERT_ID',
27   ];
28
29   const missingEnvVars = requiredEnvVars.filter(
30     (envVar) => !process.env[envVar]
31   );
32
33   if (missingEnvVars.length) {
34     return NextResponse.json(
35       {
36         error: `Missing environment variables: ${missingEnvVars.join(', ')}. Please add them to your Vercel project.`,
37       },
38       {
39         status: 500,
40       }
41     );
42   }
43
44   // get environment
45   const env = process.env.NODE_ENV ?? 'development';
46   // if not in production, do not rate limit
47   if (env !== 'production') {
48     return NextResponse.next();
49   }
50
51   const ip = request.ip ?? '127.0.0.1';
52   const { success, pending, limit, reset, remaining } = await ratelimit.limit(
53     ip
54   );
55   return success
56     ? NextResponse.next()
57     : NextResponse.json(
58       {
59         error: 'Rate limit exceeded',
60         limit,
61         remaining,
62         reset,
63       },
64       {
65         status: 429,
66       }
67     );
68 }
```

Figure 62 - Middleware Part 2

8.2.7. Vercel – CI/CD + GitHub

After the website was made, it was important to get it LIVE. Instead of going through the traditional, more expensive serverful route – serverless technology was used. More specifically, Vercel, which allows for Next.js apps to be hosted.

Deploying to Vercel is pretty simple. Environment variables and getting things deployed via Staging and Production is straight-forward. Every time a push is made to the connected GitHub repo (available at: <https://github.com/HaynesX/ai2>), Vercel detected the changes and deploys it to the URL (bought on SquareSpace domains out of the researcher’s own money) at <https://neurocar.net>.

The following diagram (Figure 63) demonstrates the flow.

Figure 63 - Vercel CI/CD Pipeline

It's also worth noting that the GitHub Repo is available for you to clone / fork SUPER EASILY. The instructions are well-detailed. If, for example, certain API keys aren't provided from the user when the user clone the repo and runs the application – appropriate error messages are provided to alert the user on what to do in case anything is missed. Extreme detail went in to making this website re-usable by others! 😊

NeuroCar

Welcome to **NeuroCar**, a sleek car prediction application designed to simplify the process of identifying car details from images. Developed by Brandon Haynes and hosted on Vercel, this app leverages the power of the ResNet50 model and OpenAI's GPT-4o to deliver accurate car identification and provide useful pricing and eBay listings for similar models.

Check out the live site: [NeuroCar](#)

🔗 Features

NeuroCar offers the following features:

- **Car Identification:** Uses a custom-trained ResNet50 neural network model to identify the make, model, and year of cars from uploaded images.
- **Pricing Information:** Integrates pricing data to give users an average price for the identified car model.
- **eBay Listings:** Fetches and displays listings from eBay that match the identified car, providing users with quick access to similar cars available for sale.

Technology Stack

- **Next.js:** A React framework for building user interfaces and static generation.
- **Vercel:** Hosting and serverless backend services for optimized performance and scalability.
- **ResNet50 Model:** A deep convolutional network used for image recognition tasks.
- **OpenAI's GPT-4V:** Utilized for processing and interpreting complex data inputs to enhance prediction accuracy.
- **App Directory Structure:** Utilizes the Next.js app directory for a streamlined project structure.

Important Notes

- **OpenAI API Tier Requirement:** To ensure full functionality of the NeuroCar application without service interruptions, you must be subscribed to the **Tier 1** plan of OpenAI's services as **GPT-4 Turbo** is required. Using the Free Tier may result in errors due to API limitations.

Getting Started

To get **NeuroCar** running locally and on Vercel, follow these detailed steps:

Figure 64 - Part of the GitHub README.md

8.3. Designs, Showcase & Video Demo

Below are the final screens (completely and fully responsive for Mobile, Desktop and Tablets, by the way!)

To see a video demo of the website, the (unlisted) link is here:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZUQtlkNNMFQ>

The first two screens (Figure 65) (Figure 66) show the animated loading page where it pulls the ResNet50 Model from the public folder.

Figure 65 - NeuroCar Loading [Desktop]

Figure 66 - NeuroCar Loading [Mobile]

Next, after the model has loaded and cached in IndexedDB in the browser, the main screen is shown (Figure 67) (Figure 68) where the user can Drag and Drop (upload) a car image to get predictions.

Figure 67 - NeuroCar Home [Desktop]

Figure 68 - NeuroCar Home [Mobile]

When an image is added to the Drag and Drop, it goes to the PredictingLoadingPage (Figure 69) (Figure 70), displaying the 1st step loading with an animated progress bar. While loading, it tries to predict the car Make Model and Year using either the ResNet50 Model or OpenAI's API (if the model can't identify the vehicle).

Figure 69 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P1 [Desktop]

Figure 70 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P1 [Mobile]

Now, if the model CAN NOT detect the vehicle's Make Model Year, it uses OpenAI's API. Below, on the second stage of the screen, it indicates what model was used as well as showing inputs to which the user can use to edit the details. In these specific images (Figure 71) (Figure 72), it uses OpenAI's API as clearly indicated.

Figure 71 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 [Desktop]

Figure 72 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 [Mobile]

However, in these images (Figure 73) (Figure 74), it uses the actual ResNet50 Model as clearly indicated.

Figure 73 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 ResNet50 [Desktop]

Figure 74 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P2 ResNet50 [Mobile]

Next, showing the final Loading state of the PredictLoadingPage while it pulls eBay listings and the average price (Figure 75) (Figure 76).

Figure 75 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P3 [Desktop]

Figure 76 - NeuroCar PredictLoading P3 [Mobile]

And, lastly, shows the final page where it provides the user with the average price of the vehicle given to the model, as well as a list of eBay listings they can go to for more info, the ability to copy the price to the clipboard, and try again if they want with a new image. (Figure 77) (Figure 76).

The screenshot displays a web interface for NeuroCar. At the top, it shows the 'Average Vehicle Price' as £20832.91. Below this, a message states: 'Below are found eBay listings of similar vehicles. The average price of these vehicles is £20832.91.' There are two buttons: 'Copy Price' and 'Try Again'. The main content consists of six car listings arranged in a 2x3 grid. Each listing includes a car image, a price, a location, and a description of the vehicle.

Price	Location	Description
£7,599.00	Used - Buckhurst Hill	2021 21 AUDI A3 TECKNIK AUTOMATIC NEW SHAPE DAMAGED SALVAGE REPAIRABLE
£15,595.00	Used - Huddersfield	2021 (21) Audi A3 35 TFSI S Line 5dr Hatchback 1.5 Petrol Manual
£22,990.00	Used - Liverpool	2021 Audi A3 40 TFSI e S Line 5dr S Tronic HATCHBACK PETROL/ELECTRIC Automatic
£17,950.00	Used - Bolton	2021 Audi A3 30 TFSI Sport 4dr SALOON PETROL Manual
£21,495.00	Used - Preston	2021 Audi A3 35 TFSI S Line 5dr HATCHBACK PETROL Manual
£19,075.00	Used - London	2021 Audi A3 30 TFSI S Line 5dr S Tronic hatchback petrol Semi Automatic

Figure 77 - NeuroCar FinalPage [Desktop]

Average Vehicle Price

£20832.91

Below are found eBay listings of similar vehicles. The average price of these vehicles is £20832.91.

[Copy Price](#) [Try Again](#)

£7,599.00
Used - Buckhurst Hill

2021 21 AUDI A3 TECKNIK AUTOMATIC NEW
SHAPE DAMAGED SALVAGE REPAIRABLE

ebay

£15,595.00
Used - Huddersfield

2021 (21) Audi A3 35 TFSI S Line 5dr

Figure 78 - NeuroCar FinalPage [Mobile]

It's worth noting that some of these UI/UX components are modified version from <https://www.nextui.pro/> and NextUI overall. The animations are custom.

It took a VERY long time to make this appealing and useful.

Furthermore, as Screenshots don't really give the site justice, a video has been uploaded showcasing the website with different images and states, etc, so it can be clearly seen how much dedicated time and effort went in to making the site.

The (unlisted) 4K Video Demo is available here:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZUQtlkNNMFQ>

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, this assignment has been a VERY challenging, yet rewarding journey. The task of understanding AND implementing a Convolutional Neural Network for vehicle make, model, and year classification was SO complex. Learning the intricacies of CNNs and how models like ResNet50 and VGG16 function within deep neural networks required a lot of research and practice. I heavily relied on ChatGPT, various academic references, and presentations from the course lecturer to grasp these concepts. Each step, from data preprocessing to model training and hyperparameter tuning had its own difficulties. The theoretical knowledge gained was mental, but applying this knowledge practically to achieve high model accuracy and reduce misclassifications was a steep learning curve.

Developing the web application added another layer of complexity but also provided a platform to showcase the model's capabilities. Using Next.js to build and deploy a live site that integrates the ResNet50 model was both time-consuming and intricate, yet it was also the MOST enjoyable part of the project (due to a solid background in web development already).

Comparing the use of PyTorch and TensorFlow, I found TensorFlow more user-friendly, mainly due to its extensive documentation. This project not only honed the technical skills in machine learning and web dev, but also highlighted the importance of passion and continuous learning in tackling complex problems. The final product, accessible at <https://neurocar.net>, is a testament to the hard work and dedication invested in this assignment, providing a practical tool for vehicle classification and price estimation. 😊

9.1. Further Research

In regard to any further research, I would say that finding better ways to get the dataset in a good position would be my first area of improvement, as it was so time-consuming – there must be more efficient ways to deal with that.. But overall, the assignment given was one of the best!

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11. Appendices

(Appendix 1) VGG19 Training:

```

Epoch 1/10
322/322 [=====] - 190s 557ms/step - loss: 2.3145 - accuracy: 0.4139 - val_loss: 0.8396 - val_accuracy: 0.8017
Epoch 2/10
322/322 [=====] - 86s 264ms/step - loss: 1.3325 - accuracy: 0.5907 - val_loss: 0.7986 - val_accuracy: 0.7694
Epoch 3/10
322/322 [=====] - 75s 230ms/step - loss: 1.1124 - accuracy: 0.6503 - val_loss: 0.5413 - val_accuracy: 0.8768
Epoch 4/10
322/322 [=====] - 76s 232ms/step - loss: 1.0032 - accuracy: 0.6922 - val_loss: 0.3865 - val_accuracy: 0.9218
Epoch 5/10
322/322 [=====] - 82s 251ms/step - loss: 0.9369 - accuracy: 0.7136 - val_loss: 0.3915 - val_accuracy: 0.9231
Epoch 6/10
322/322 [=====] - 85s 262ms/step - loss: 0.8810 - accuracy: 0.7325 - val_loss: 0.4886 - val_accuracy: 0.8727
Epoch 7/10
322/322 [=====] - 75s 230ms/step - loss: 0.8647 - accuracy: 0.7372 - val_loss: 0.5230 - val_accuracy: 0.8627
Epoch 8/10
322/322 [=====] - 86s 263ms/step - loss: 0.8563 - accuracy: 0.7442 - val_loss: 0.4622 - val_accuracy: 0.8913
Epoch 9/10
322/322 [=====] - 76s 234ms/step - loss: 0.8198 - accuracy: 0.7572 - val_loss: 0.3242 - val_accuracy: 0.9454
Epoch 10/10
322/322 [=====] - 86s 262ms/step - loss: 0.8257 - accuracy: 0.7544 - val_loss: 0.5413 - val_accuracy: 0.8590
<keras.src.callbacks.History at 0x7aaa2025ee90>

```

(Appendix 2) VGG16 Training:

After 8K Images on VGG16 0.2 val 32 BATCH_SIZE 15 EPOCHS NO CLASS BALANCING

```

Epoch 1/15
466/466 [=====] - 53s 110ms/step - loss: 1.8111 - accuracy: 0.3672 - val_loss: 1.1756 - val_accuracy: 0.7308
Epoch 2/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 1.4425 - accuracy: 0.4752 - val_loss: 0.9451 - val_accuracy: 0.8565
Epoch 3/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 1.2929 - accuracy: 0.5323 - val_loss: 0.9256 - val_accuracy: 0.8356
Epoch 4/15
466/466 [=====] - 51s 110ms/step - loss: 1.2057 - accuracy: 0.5626 - val_loss: 0.7952 - val_accuracy: 0.9076
Epoch 5/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 1.1440 - accuracy: 0.5853 - val_loss: 0.7056 - val_accuracy: 0.9221
Epoch 6/15
466/466 [=====] - 51s 110ms/step - loss: 1.0823 - accuracy: 0.6108 - val_loss: 0.7483 - val_accuracy: 0.9119
Epoch 7/15
466/466 [=====] - 51s 109ms/step - loss: 1.0487 - accuracy: 0.6224 - val_loss: 0.7932 - val_accuracy: 0.8753
Epoch 8/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 1.0106 - accuracy: 0.6343 - val_loss: 0.7024 - val_accuracy: 0.9038
Epoch 9/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 1.0048 - accuracy: 0.6354 - val_loss: 0.6857 - val_accuracy: 0.9323
Epoch 10/15
466/466 [=====] - 51s 109ms/step - loss: 0.9687 - accuracy: 0.6498 - val_loss: 0.5775 - val_accuracy: 0.9404
Epoch 11/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 0.9581 - accuracy: 0.6546 - val_loss: 0.6161 - val_accuracy: 0.9355
Epoch 12/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 0.9574 - accuracy: 0.6566 - val_loss: 0.7421 - val_accuracy: 0.8522
Epoch 13/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 0.9356 - accuracy: 0.6639 - val_loss: 0.6202 - val_accuracy: 0.9232
Epoch 14/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 0.9231 - accuracy: 0.6692 - val_loss: 0.5991 - val_accuracy: 0.9258
Epoch 15/15
466/466 [=====] - 52s 110ms/step - loss: 0.8965 - accuracy: 0.6796 - val_loss: 0.5573 - val_accuracy: 0.9328

```